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RIGOUROUS -
secuRe desIGn and deplOyment of trUsthwoRthy
cOntinUum computing 6G Services

Deliverable 4.1

**DESIGN PLAN OF THE AI-DRIVEN ANOMALY
DETECTION, DECISION AND MITIGATION**

Title	Design Plan of the AI-driven Anomaly Detection, Decision and Mitigation
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1 LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Explanation/Definition
5GS	5G System
5GTN	OULU's 5G Test Network
6GS	6G System
AAE	Adversarial Autoencoder
ACK	Acknowledgment
AE	Autoencoder
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AID	AI-driven Decision
AKMA	Authentication and Key Management for Applications
B5G	5G and beyond
BEST	Battery Efficient Security for very low throughput Machine Type Communication (MTC) devices
CAE	Convolutional Autoencoder
CDOM	Cognitive Decision, Orchestration, and Management
CDP	Cisco Discovery Protocol
CITEF	Cyber Integration, Test and Evaluation Framework
CL	Continual Learning
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CPS	Cyber-Physical System
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CTI	Cyber Threat Information
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DevSecOps	Development, Security, and Operations
DL	Deep Learning
DM	Data Monitoring
DoS	Denial of Service
DP	Differential Privacy
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
DS	Data Services
DSC	Dynamic and automated Service Composition
DT	Digital Twins
E2E	End-to-End
EaaS	Encryption-as-a-Service
EAP	Extensible Authentication Protocol
EDoS	Economical Denial of Sustainability
FED AI	Federated AI Anomaly Detection
FL	Federated Learning

GAT	Graph Attention
GBA	General Bootstrapping Architecture
GENEVE	Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GRE	Generic Routing Encapsulation
GRU	Gated Recurrent Unit
GTP	GPRS Tunnelling Protocol
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HE	Homomorphic Encryption
HLA	High-Level Architecture
HSPF	Holistic Security and Privacy Framework
ICMP	Internet Control Message Protocol
ICS	Industrial Control Systems
IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IIoT	Industrial IoT
IoT	Internet of Things
IoT SP	IoT Service Provider
IT/OT	Information and Operation Technology
LLDP	Link-Layer Discovery Protocol
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MISP	Threat Intelligence Sharing Platform
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MSE	Mean Square Error
MSPL	Medium-Level Security Policy Language
MTC	Machine Type Communication
MTD	Moving Target Defense
MTD	Moving Target Defense
NAI	Network Access Identifier
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NIDS	Network Intrusion Detection System
NPN	Non-Public Network
NSFM	Network Security Flow Monitoring
OAM	Operations, Administration, and Management
PC	Physical Correlator
PETs	Privacy Enhancing Technologies
RAN	Radio Access Network
REST	Representational State Transfer

RM	Response Mitigation
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
SAE	Security Analytics Engine
SCA	Slicing Control Agent
SDN	Software Defined Networks
SIEM	Security Information and Event Management
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMPS	Slicing Mitigation Planner Service
SNMP	Simple Network Management Protocol
SO	Security Orchestrator
SOAR	Security, Orchestration, Administration, and Response
SSLA	Security Service Level Agreement
SUCI	Subscription Concealed Identifier
TEDP	Tree Exploration Discovery Protocol
TEFS	Trust Evaluation and enabler Service Function
TIA	Topology Inventory Agent
TIP	Threat Intelligence Platform
TRA	Threat Risk Assessor
TTP	Tactics, Technics, and Procedures
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
UE	User Equipment
VAE	Variational Autoencoder
vCDN	virtual Content Delivery Network
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VXLAN	Virtual Extensible LAN
WMI	Windows Management Instrumentation
WPS	Wi-Fi Protected Setup
ZTM	Zero Trust Model
ZTS	Zero Trust Security

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4 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the first analysis and design of RIGOUROUS's assets aiming at enabling AI-driven anomaly detection, decision, and mitigation in RIGOUROUS framework. The design of those assets is driven by the necessity of empowering timely detection and mitigation of anomalies to deal with the stringent reliability and availability needs of 5G and beyond (B5G)/6G networks and services. To this end, emerging Artificial Intelligence (AI) approaches, including Deep Learning (DL), Federated Learning (FL) and Transfer Learning, are adopted to deliver fully automated anomaly detection, decision-making and mitigation services.

The assets are grouped into six categories according to their functions and the services they provide in the context of anomaly detection, decision, and mitigation in B5G/6G environments. The following six categories are defined:

- The assets that enable *collaborative anomaly detection while fostering privacy preservation*. Those assets intend for evolving the state-of-the-art of anomaly detection in B5G/6G from different angles, including the learning approaches adopted, the improvements to FL aggregation procedure, and the reinforcement of privacy protection in the FL framework. In fact, the assets in this category harness the potential of emerging AI approaches, such as DL, and FL, to enhance the effectiveness and timeliness of anomaly detection. Their goal is to detect anomalies that may target different planes (i.e., Control Plane and User Plane), different network communication layers, and different B5G/6G applications/services. Additionally, tackling the problems of stragglers (i.e., slow clients involved in FL process) and catastrophic forgetting in FL are under the radar of some assets, where a novel aggregation procedure and the use of Continual Learning are envisioned. Moreover, the assets in this category, incorporate a range of Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs), such as Homomorphic Encryption, Differential Privacy and Zero-Knowledge Proof, to promote privacy-preservation within the FL process.
- The assets that provide *cognitive security decision-making, orchestration and management* services. This comprises an AI-driven physical correlator that provides relevant AI-derived physical network parameters and data, allowing a more comprehensive assessment of cybersecurity threats. It encompasses also an AI-driven decision-making service that leverages advanced AI-assisted mechanisms and algorithms and the outcomes of other assets (e.g., the anomaly detection and physical correlator assets) for autonomously identifying the nature of cyberthreats and selecting the most suitable security mitigation plan to counteract them. This category includes also assets for enabling zero-touch secure Internet of Things (IoT) device bootstrapping, trusted application onboarding through certificates, and the creation of security policy based on trust evaluation.
- The assets that leverage AI and/or rule-based methods to provide *security response and mitigation* capabilities. This includes an asset for proactively mitigating Economical Denial of Sustainability (EDoS) attacks by adopting a novel DL-powered forecasting-based approach for detecting malicious resource scaling requests. It also incorporates an AI-based risk management asset that provides advanced capabilities for threat prioritization, risk indices calculation, and recommendation of tailored mitigation strategies. Additionally, this category comprises assets that aim at enabling dynamic and automated service composition to address

interconnection issues and planning of network slicing mitigation policies for real-time mitigation of cyberthreats.

- The assets offering cutting-edge network flow and topology monitoring services that can be deployed alongside the data plane for effective detection of cyberattacks within a 5G network infrastructure as well as enabling subsequent actions to mitigate threats. The assets in this category are instrumental for achieving RIGOUROUS's vision of establishing Security, Orchestration, Administration, and Response (SOAR) closed loops.
- The assets that strengthen *AI robustness* and improve *privacy preservation*; two key requisites to foster trust in AI. Particularly, this category includes an asset dedicated to enabling proactive safeguarding of ML models against poisoning attacks through a Moving Target Defense (MTD) strategy. It also encompasses an asset for providing a cloud-native based Encryption as a Service (EaaS) platform that offers cryptographic services to IoT devices/gateways. The EaaS platform is also envisioned to provide homomorphic encryption services that can be outsourced to build privacy-preserving AI/ML models that can process encrypted data. This category involves also an asset for empowering privacy-preserving Cyber Threat Information (CTI) sharing, leveraging various PETs (e.g., K-anonymity, T-closeness, and suppression) for anonymizing the CTI information generated by RIGOUROUS modules before their sharing.
- The assets that facilitate security testing by providing services that enable the simulation of physical spaces by replicating digital twins and creating cyber-range environments. This includes a digital twin that can simulate real-time transmission of data from heterogeneous sources, allowing to generate a topology that can be leveraged by the "dynamic and automated service composition" asset to detect mismatches between the interacting components with regard to interoperability, security, privacy, and trust requirements. It includes also a cyber integration, test, and evaluation framework that can emulate an exact representation of complex and critical networking infrastructures and defining complex attack scenarios, allowing rapid validation of the overall security posture of RIGOUROUS framework.

Each of these categories constitutes a section within this document. Within a section, and for each of the category's assets, there is first an emphasis on the innovations it introduces in comparison to the current state-of-the-art, followed by a detailed description of the asset, elaborating on its functional workflow and the key enabling technologies adopted to implement the asset's services. Each section is then concluded by discussing the positioning of the category's assets to the functional block(s) of RIGOUROUS' high-level architecture described in D2.1.

5 INTRODUCTION

WP4 aims to design and develop advanced mechanisms that leverage the potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to empower automatic anomaly detection, decision, and mitigation services. This deliverable provides the initial outcomes coming from all the tasks in WP4, including the first analysis and design of RIGOUROUS's assets developed within WP4's tasks to enable AI-driven anomaly detection, decision, and mitigation in RIGOUROUS framework.

WP4 assets are classified into six (06) categories based on their functionalities and the services they are delivering:

- The assets that aim at enabling privacy-preserving collaborative anomaly detection. Those assets leverage the potential of Deep Learning (DL) and Federated Learning (FL) to boost the effectiveness and timeliness of anomaly detection. Furthermore, they adopt various Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs) to foster privacy-preservation in FL process.
- The assets that enable cognitive security decision-making, orchestration, and management. This includes assets for autonomous identification of the cyber threats' nature and determination of the most appropriate approach to mitigate them, AI-assisted correlation of physical network parameters and data, zero-touch secure IoT device bootstrapping, certificate-based trusted application onboarding, as well as security policy generation based on trust evaluation.
- The assets that exploit AI and/or rule-based techniques to deliver security response and mitigation capabilities. The assets in this category aim at proactive mitigation of Economical Denial of Sustainability (EDoS) attacks, dynamic and automated service composition to tackle interconnection problems, intelligent risk management, and planning of slicing mitigation policies for real-time mitigation of cyber threats.
- The assets that provide advanced network flow and topology monitoring services, allowing the establishment of Security, Orchestration, Administration, and Response (SOAR) closed loops.
- The assets that bolster AI robustness and enhance privacy protection. More specifically, the assets in this category focus on enabling proactive protection of ML models against poisoning attacks using Moving Target Defense (MTD) paradigm, providing encryption as a Service (EaaS), and empowering privacy-preserving Cyber Threat Information (CTI) sharing.
- The assets that enable security testing by providing services that allow simulating the physical space by reproducing digital twins and creating cyber-range environments. Such services are crucial for identifying security issues between interacting entities in an IoT environment as well as validating the overall security posture of RIGOUROUS framework.

For each asset, we highlight the advancements brought by the asset compared to the state of the art, provide a detailed description of the asset and its mapping to functional block(s) of RIGOUROUS's high-level architecture (HLA) described in D2.1. Figure 1 illustrates the overall mapping between the 6 categories of WP4 assets and the HLA's functional blocks, indicating in which section of the deliverable the assets of each category are described.

Figure 1 - Mapping of WP4 assets to functional blocks of RIGOROUS HLA.

The main structure of this deliverable is summarized as follows:

- Section 3 elaborates on the AI-driven privacy-preserving federated anomaly detection assets;
- Section 4 introduces the AI-driven attack cognitive decision-making, orchestration, and management assets;
- Section 5 describes the AI-driven security response-mitigation assets;
- Section 6 presents the SOAR-driven network flow and topology monitoring assets;
- Section 7 specifies the assets devised for empowering robust and privacy-preserving AI;
- Section 8 details the assets enabling cybersecurity testing and digital twinning;
- Section 9 concludes this deliverable.

6 AI-DRIVEN FEDERATED ANOMALY DETECTION

6.1. Introduction

A timely detection and prediction of anomalies and intrusions in the network is crucial to cater to the strict reliability and availability needs of 5G and beyond (B5G) networks. In fact, the prompt anomaly identification allows for a swift response to mitigate the detected issue, counteracting severe attack damage, service degradation and financial losses [1]. ML techniques, especially Deep Learning (DL) techniques, are a key enabler in meeting this goal, allowing to build effective detection systems that can recognize complex abnormal traffic patterns in time-varying multi-dimensional data [2]. Furthermore, the highly distributed nature of B5G networks makes distributed learning, particularly Federated Learning (FL), a promising approach for fostering privacy-preserving collaborative anomaly detection at the edge. Indeed, using FL will bring about a significant improvement in the effectiveness and timeliness of anomaly detection, owing to local knowledge sharing among cooperating entities. In addition, limiting information exchange to the model parameters promotes data privacy preservation, a fundamental requirement for complying with data sharing regulations in B5G networks. Despite the privacy protection enabled by FL, private data exposure is still possible [2][3]. Addressing this concern calls for the integration of FL with Privacy-Enhancing Technologies (PETs) such as homomorphic encryption (HE), differential privacy (DP), and zero-knowledge proofs. This combination is instrumental in fostering privacy-preserving FL-based anomaly detection in B5G networks.

Stimulated by the above-mentioned observations, RIGOUROUS is developing a set of innovative privacy-preserving federated DL-based anomaly detection assets that aim at advancing the existing state-of-the-art of anomaly detection in B5G from different perspectives, including the learning approaches adopted, the enhancements to FL aggregation procedure, and the improvement of privacy protection for FL framework.

As illustrated in Figure 2, the devised assets are complementary by aiming at identifying anomalies/attacks that can target different planes (i.e., Control Plane and User Plane), different network communication layers, and different applications (e.g., Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) and web-based 5G services). The assets can be used in tandem to enable a holistic defence against cyber threats that may target various network segments. Furthermore, the assets designed to counter identical cyber-threats within the same plane/layer can be selectively used to respond to various security service level agreement (SSLA). In fact, the AI-enabled security as a Service vision adopted by RIGOUROUS allows to Security Orchestrator to provision the appropriate anomaly detection asset that meets the desired SSLA. For instance, to protect against application-layer DDoS attacks, if the SSLA specifies that both data confidentiality and high accuracy should be guaranteed, the FL-based anomaly detection asset that adopts HE for privacy preservation can be selected. Otherwise, if the SSLA mandates data anonymization guarantees, with a tolerance for slight loss in accuracy, then the FL-based anomaly detection asset utilizing DP approach can be chosen.

Figure 2 - Attack Surface Targeted by RIGOUROUS Anomaly Detection Assets.

The remaining of this section elaborates on RIGOUROUS’s anomaly detection assets and their mapping to functional blocks of RIGOUROUS’s high-level architecture. For each asset, we emphasize the advancements brought by the asset compared to state-of-the-art, and provide a detailed description of the asset, highlighting the anomaly/attacks addressed, the learning approach and algorithms adopted to build the anomaly detection model, and the PETs used to foster privacy preservation.

6.2. Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector

6.2.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

There are numerous advantages associated with 5G networks and their applications such as the IoT; however, there are also some limitations, including resource constraints and vulnerabilities related to privacy and security [4][5]. As threats become more complex, traditional centralized anomaly detection methods are inadequate [6]. Due to the centralization of sensitive data, these methods are inflexible and may compromise the privacy of individuals [7]. As a solution to these issues, FL techniques are recommended for 5G environments [4]. By sharing parameters and local models instead of raw data, FL improves privacy and reduces training time. Nevertheless, FL methods are also susceptible to security risks such as data poisoning and model inference [1]. A potential solution for improving the privacy of FL for anomaly detection in 5G is Homomorphic Encryption (HE) [8].

In the context of RIGOUROUS, we present an innovative hybrid FL approach that preserves privacy while leveraging the latest advancements in this field in order to detect various types of cyber-attacks against IIoT and 5G services. To address the importance of real-time in IIoT, our solution focuses on mitigating stragglers in synchronous FL and optimizing communication costs in asynchronous FL, areas that have received relatively little research. In addition, the asset aims to counteract the catastrophic forgetting issue, where prior knowledge is forgotten while sequentially learning new attack patterns from a stream of data. Few studies (e.g.,[9][10][11])

have addressed catastrophic forgetting issue in network anomaly detection using Continual Learning (CL), but focusing on centralized models rather than FL. In RIGOUROUS, we intend to fill this gap by integrating CL with FL to empower sustainable and cooperative privacy-preserving network anomaly detection in B5G networks.

A major goal of this asset is to use DL-based privacy-preserving FL for anomaly detection in order to achieve high detection accuracy and fast convergence, while preventing privacy leakage.

6.2.2. Asset Description

In Figure 3, a high-level architecture of the asset has been shown. The asset is composed of two modules: industrial agents and an aggregation server. Industrial agents represent owners of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs). A third authority generates public and private keys first. Through iterative interactions with the aggregation server, industrial agents construct a local DL model using their own industrial CPS data, encrypt it, and update its parameters. The aggregation server aggregates the encrypted model parameters from each industrial agent. Aggregated encrypted parameters are then sent back to industrial agents. By decrypting the aggregated parameters, industrial agents update their DL models. To obtain a final level of perfect intrusion detection model accuracy, multiple rounds of interaction between the aggregator server and each industrial agent are required.

Figure 3 - Functional architecture of Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector asset.

In the proposed hybrid FL, the synchronous FL and asynchronous FL strategies are combined in some way to eliminate stragglers and communication bottlenecks. In addition, a novel approach is used to define a threshold based on training time to determine which clients will be able to participate in the next round of hybrid FL.

The model to be used in the Attack Classification is a basic Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) neural network and Convolution Neural Network (CNN) trained with labelled data. This data contains the considered attack types as labels.

Regarding privacy preservation during the FL process, we propose to use HE mechanisms to ensure data/parameter confidentiality of exchanged models to mitigate eavesdropping on the model parameters and inference model risks. A partial HE is used. Partial HE is a type of HE that permits both the addition and multiplication of ciphertexts. It is preferred nowadays to use partial HE since it is faster than Fully HE, and in most cases, it is sufficient for homomorphic calculations, especially for FLs that only require addition and multiplication.

Input data are two datasets with a list of features related to Industrial Control Systems (ICS) and network flow whose values specify normal behaviour or abnormal behaviour in order to train the implied model. For attacks against 5G services (e.g., a virtual Content Delivery Network (vCDN) [12]), we consider 5G-NIDD dataset that contains a combination of malicious and legitimate traffic generated by actual mobile devices attached to the OULU's 5G Test Network (5GTN¹) through two base stations. The malicious traffic is generated by several Network-layer and application-layer DoS/DDoS attacks.

The output is the result of accuracy anomaly detection and convergence speed (the number of iterations that are used to reach a target accuracy). The FL mechanism also requires some input parameters, which include the number of training iterations, the number of epochs to be performed by each node in each iteration, and the learning rate. In Table 1, a summary of asset details can be consulted. Here we include information about the attack scenarios and datasets to be used for model evaluation.

Table 1 - Summary of details related to Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector asset.

Anomaly Targeted	Attacks Considered	AI/ML Technique(s)	Dataset(s)	ML Model's Inputs	ML Model's Output	PET (s)
Cyber-attacks against ICS	Cyber threats against industrial systems (DoS, Reconnaissance, Command injection, and Backdoor attack), Cyber Threats against FL Framework (Eavesdropping on the model parameters)	DL (CNN, MLP), FL, CL	- Gas Pipeline, - WUSTL-IloT	MODBUS Network traffic features from a gas pipeline industrial control system	Attack Label (in multi-class classification), and being normal or attack (in binary-class classification)	HE
5G network intrusion detection	- Network-layer DoS/DDoS - Application-layer DoS/DDoS		- 5G-NIDD	Network flow features		

¹ <https://5gtn.fi/>

6.3. Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection

6.3.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

Over the last few years, several works have demonstrated that Signature-based Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS), which are currently the most widely used option, are ineffective at detecting zero-day attacks or variations in known attack patterns [13]. Given the increasing sophistication of attacks in next-gen networks and environments, better adapted detection systems are needed to protect them. In this line, ML- and DL-based anomaly detection systems have proven to be more appropriate to these application scenarios, and some proposals have been presented recently [13][14]. In addition, the combination with Federated Learning for model training can enhance some aspects such as privacy and efficiency [16]. This has gained a lot of research interest recently, and some articles [5][17] propose its application over IoT and 5G environments. Others, such as [18], explore the application of privacy-preserving techniques, which in this case are Differential Privacy mechanisms, to protect the exchange of model updates between clients and aggregators during the Federated Learning process, thus preventing membership inference attacks, which represent an important challenge in the majority of Federated Learning schemes deployments [19].

In the context of RIGOUROUS, we propose a privacy-preserving federated-learning-based framework that brings together all the latest state-of-the-art advancements regarding this type of systems. In addition, our asset will explore detection of attacks against not only user plane but also control plane, where the existing literature is rather weak, and will integrate with the AI-based Security Orchestrator so its main components can be deployed, configured and re-configured if necessary in real-time and based on the infrastructure needs, thus achieving a fully adaptable and more accurate detection system that is constantly updated with the current threat status of the network.

6.3.2. Asset Description

The asset is composed by the following three modules:

1. **Federated Learning Agent:** deployed in the Infrastructure Layer as a Security Agent, it will collect network flow statistics from Data Monitoring module and train a model along with a central aggregator and other agents deployed in the network, once enough samples have been collected.
2. **Federated Learning Aggregator:** also deployed in the Infrastructure Layer as a Security Agent, it will coordinate the group of Federated Learning Agents and will employ a certain fusion algorithm to merge all the incoming model updates. At the end of the learning process, it will provide the final model to the Data Monitoring module from the Monitoring and Analytics plane.
3. **AI-based Real-time Anomaly Detection Engine:** deployed within the AI-driven Security Analytics Engine (SAE), it is composed by two submodules: first, an Anomaly Detection Engine, which will perform real-time anomaly detection from real traffic, and second, an

Attack Classification Engine, that will classify the anomalous flows into known attack categories, sending this information to the Decision Engine. Both modules will employ a Deep Learning model previously trained by the FL Agents and received through the Data Monitoring and Data Services modules. If a certain anomalous flow cannot be labelled with a known attack category, it will be classified as an unknown/zero-day attack.

The model to be used in the Anomaly Detection Engine is a Deep Autoencoder that will be trained with normal, non-anomalous traffic flows. Since this type of model aims to reconstruct the input in the output, it will become good at reconstructing the non-anomalous flow samples, so that when a malicious flow is evaluated against the model, the reconstruction error will be high. An error threshold will be defined at the end of the training process and will be used to classify a certain traffic flow as an anomaly. Consequently, the network should run in a controlled mode during the training, making sure no malicious traffic is being generated by any point in the network, to avoid the poisoning of the model and therefore optimize the detection accuracy.

On the other hand, the model to be used in the Attack Classification Engine is a MLP trained with labelled data. This data will contain the considered attack types as labels.

Regarding privacy preservation during FL process, we propose to use Differential Privacy mechanisms to add noise to the exchanged model updates to mitigate membership inference risks. Several noise adding mechanisms such as Gaussian, Laplace or some of their variations will be considered for this purpose.

In Figure 4, the architecture of the asset that has been previously described is shown. Moreover, in Table 2, a summary of asset details can be consulted. Here we include information about the attack scenarios and datasets to be used for model evaluation.

Figure 4 - Function architecture of Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection (UMU).

Table 2 - Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection (UMU) summary of details.

Anomaly Targeted	Attacks Considered	AI/ML Technique(s)	Dataset(s)	ML Model's Inputs	ML Model's Output	PET(s)
Abnormal deviation from non-anomalous network flow features	User and control plane attacks	Deep Autoencoder, MLP, Federated Learning	5G-NIDD, ToN-IoT, own (not available yet)	Network flow features	Attack Label	Differential Privacy

6.4. Holistic Security and Privacy Framework

6.4.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

In the ever-evolving landscape of Intrusion Detection Systems, the state of the art is characterized by the increased use of Federated Learning. This employment ranges greatly in the choice of Machine Learning technique used, being that some that we deem more relevant are those which utilize AutoEncoders. Due to their learning method of reconstruction of data they are extremely valuable in Anomaly Detection scenarios.

For example, Meryem et al. [20] introduce Fed-ANIDS, a FL framework for anomaly-based network intrusion detection systems using autoencoders. It addresses the limitations of centralised ML-based AD methods by preserving data privacy and handling heterogeneous datasets. They evaluate the framework with three datasets (USTC-TFC2016², CIC-IDS2017³, CSE-CIC-IDS2018⁴), three Auto-Encoder variations (Autoencoder (AE), Variational Autoencoder (VAE), Adversarial Autoencoder (AAE)), and two local model aggregation approaches (FedAvg, FedProx). For USTC-TFC2016, AAE with FedProx achieves the best result, with an f1-score of 99.94%. For CIC-IDS2017, a simple AE with FedProx outperformed others, with a 92.73% f1-score, whilst for CSE-CIC-IDS2018, a VAE with FedProx reached 90.65% f1-score. The proposed approach consistently outperforms baseline algorithms, highlighting FedProx's effectiveness. The authors emphasise the feasibility of using autoencoders for large-scale intrusion detection systems.

ZiXuan et al. [21] as well present a FL approach combined with Convolutional Autoencoders (CAE) for anomaly detection in Software Defined Networks (SDN). As an evaluation metric they utilized the CIC-IDS2017³, a locally trained CAE a Federated trained CAE then utilizing model based on Basic AutoEncoder and Stacked Autoencoder to use as the benchmark model to evaluate the performance of the CAE model, and for a classification method they utilized Mean Square Error (MSE) to evaluate the difference between the model's predicted value and the actual value, being

² <https://github.com/yungshenglu/USTC-TFC2016>

³ <https://www.unb.ca/cic/datasets/ids-2017.html>

⁴ <https://www.unb.ca/cic/datasets/ids-2018.html>

that the selection threshold would be equal to the loss value of the last round when there was a model training conversion. As a result, they experienced that under the same test conditions the precision, accuracy and AUC all improved from the local CAE model to the FL-CAE by 14%, 20% and 10% respectively. The same was maintained when comparing FL-AE and the FL-CAE, where the FL-CAE accuracy was 4% higher and the AUC had a 1% improvement.

Under the scope of RIGOUROUS, this framework is envisioned to go beyond the existent state of the art by exploring PETs such as Zero-Knowledge Proofs and Differential Privacy. Such techniques aim to increase the existent data privacy level in FL, as well as to increase the trust level between the different federated parties. Additionally, this framework will explore further aggregation methods beyond the traditional ones (i.e., arithmetic average). Furthermore, it is foreseen the development of a fault-tolerant system capable of handling federated agent failures (namely, during the FL training), ensuring the integrity and reliability of the entire process. This comprehensive strategy represents a significant advancement in FL, promising heightened privacy and enhanced system resilience in challenging operational scenarios.

6.4.2. Asset Description

The Holistic Security and Privacy Framework (HSPF) is composed of three main components: (i) Aggregator, (ii) Collector, and (iii) Agent.

The Aggregator corresponds to the main framework Unit, being responsible for coordinating the Federated Training procedure. It performs the management and distribution of the different ML models used for anomaly detection by the different federated agents, saving in the database the different training iterations of these models for analysis and comparison purposes. Along with this, the Aggregator is also responsible for the enrolment of the different Services that will be accompanied by the Agent and Collector components.

The Agent component, where the federated agent resides, is responsible for inferring the inbound and outbound traffic and training accordingly, being the network traffic collected by the Collector. It also is the main trainee of the Federated Training procedure along with other Agent components inserted in applications of the same type which are utilizing the same ML model.

Both components, the Agent and the Collector, are injected as sidecars next to any existing container where the to-be-secured application is executing. Figure 5 presents the HSPF functional architecture, displaying the interactions among these three components.

Figure 5 - HSPF functional architecture.

The HSPF is also prepared to handle multiple applications in multiple environments, with the possibility of having a centralised Aggregator managing all the different HSPF components.

The HSPF detection engine is based on an AutoEncoder approach, which leverages the reconstruction error provided by this ML method in conjunction with a dynamic threshold as a way to distinguish between normal and malicious traffic. Table 3 summarises some key aspects of the HSPF.

Table 3 - HSPF key aspects.

Anomaly Targeted	Attacks Considered	AI/ML Technique(s)	Dataset(s)	ML Model's Inputs	ML Model's Output	PET(s)
Layer 4 attacks against network applications in K8s clusters	DoS Hulk, PortScan, DDoS, DoS, GoldenEye, FTP-Patator, SSH-Patator, DoS Slowloris, DoS Slowhttptest, Bot, Web Attack - Brute Force, Web Attack -	AutoEncoder (Traditional and Convolutional)	CIC-IDS2017 CSE-CIC-IDS2018	Network flow features	Network flow features	Zero Knowledge Proof Differential Privacy

XSS, Infiltration, Web Attack - SQL Injection, Heartbleed						
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Inbound and Outbound data

The inbound data received by the HSPF corresponds to network traffic flows collected by the HSPF Collector component using the NFStream plugin⁵. The set of collected features has been aligned with the group of features present in the CIC-IDS2017 dataset³ since it is one of the reference datasets commonly found in the literature for the theme of anomaly detection and security, and also considering the need for common ground to enable the post-hoc performance comparison between the implemented ML approaches and already existent works.

The HSPF outbound data corresponds to reporting messages sent to an Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) broker or Representational State Transfer (REST) endpoint whenever a set of anomalies is classified as an attack. Such messages include several fields, namely the original network features values, as illustrated in Figure 6, which presents the message schema (on the left) and an example (on the right).

```

{
  "anomalies": [
    {
      "source_ip": "48.54.23.90",
      "destination_ip": "172.24.0.14",
      "destination_port": 443,
      "flow_filename": "../eth0-collection.txt",
      "flow_id": 4,
      "flow_data": "[[\"133\", \"10.244.2.249\", \"45998\", \"10.244.1.119\", \"443\", \"6\", \"2023-09-25 14:59:31.490\", \"0.327\", \"11\", \"0\", \"1918\", \"0\", \"756\", \"66\", \"174.36363636363637\", \"228.1009744509097\", \"0\", \"0\", \"0.0\", \"0.0\", \"5865.4434250764525\", \"33.63914373088685\", \"322\", \"32.7\", \"0\", \"101.6519661593024\", \"327\", \"32.7\", \"101.6519661593024\", \"322\", \"0\", \"0.0\", \"0.0\", \"0\", \"1\", \"0\", \"0\", \"0\", \"502\", \"0\", \"33.63914373088685\", \"0\", \"66\", \"756\", \"174.36363636363637\", \"228.1009744509097\", \"47300.04958677686\", \"1\", \"1\", \"0\", \"4\", \"10\", \"0\", \"0\", \"0.0\", \"174.36363636363637\", \"174.36363636363637\", \"0.0\", \"0.0\", \"0\", \"0\", \"11\", \"1918\", \"0\", \"0\", \"20\", \"0\", \"4\", \"66\", \"1500.0\", \"500.0\", \"2000.0\", \"1000.0\", \"108333.33333333331\", \"151085.7004772708\", \"322000.0\", \"1000.0\", \"11\"]"]",
    },
    {
      "source_ip": "48.54.23.93",
      "destination_ip": "172.24.0.14",
      "destination_port": 80,
      "flow_filename": "../eth0-collection.txt",
      "flow_id": 7,
      "flow_data": "[\"STRING\"]",
    },
    {
      "source_ip": "48.54.23.90",
      "destination_ip": "172.24.0.14",
      "destination_port": 8080,
      "flow_filename": "../eth0-collection.txt",
      "flow_id": 20,
      "flow_data": "[\"STRING\"]",
    }
  ],
  "detection_details": {
    "classifier_ip": "172.24.0.15",
    "flow_features": "[\"id\", \"src_ip\", \"src_port\", \"dst_ip\", \"dst_port\", \"protocol\", \"timestamp\", \"udps_flow_duration\", \"src2dst_packets\", \"dst2src_packets\", \"udps_totlen_fwd_pkts\", \"udps_totlen_bwd_pkts\", \"src2dst_max_ps\", \"src2dst_min_ps\", \"src2dst_mean_ps\", \"src2dst_stddev_ps\", \"dst2src_min_ps\", \"dst2src_max_ps\", \"dst2src_mean_ps\", \"dst2src_stddev_ps\", \"udps_flow_bytes_s\", \"udps_flow_pkts_s\", \"udps_flow_lat_max\", \"udps_flow_lat_mean\", \"udps_flow_lat_std\", \"udps_flow_lat_tot\", \"src2dst_mean_plat_ms\", \"src2dst_stddev_plat_ms\", \"src2dst_max_plat_ms\", \"src2dst_min_plat_ms\", \"udps_bwd_lat_tot\", \"dst2src_mean_plat_ms\", \"dst2src_stddev_plat_ms\", \"dst2src_max_plat_ms\", \"dst2src_min_plat_ms\", \"src2dst_psh_packets\", \"dst2src_psh_packets\", \"src2dst_urg_packets\", \"dst2src_urg_packets\", \"udps_fwd_header_len\", \"udps_bwd_header_len\", \"udps_fwd_pkts_s\", \"udps_bwd_pkts_s\", \"udps_pkt_len_min\", \"udps_pkt_len_max\", \"udps_pkt_len_mean\", \"udps_pkt_len_std\", \"udps_pkt_len_var\", \"udps_fin_flag_cnt\", \"udps_syn_flag_cnt\", \"udps_rst_flag_cnt\", \"udps_psh_flag_cnt\", \"udps_ack_flag_cnt\", \"udps_urg_flag_cnt\", \"udps_cw_flag_cnt\", \"udps_ece_flag_cnt\", \"udps_down_up_ratio\", \"udps_pkt_size_avg\", \"udps_fwd_seg_size_avg\", \"udps_bwd_seg_size_avg\", \"udps_fwd_bytes_b_avg\", \"udps_bwd_bytes_b_avg\", \"udps_fwd_bk_rate_avg\", \"udps_bwd_bk_rate_avg\", \"udps_bwd_pkts_b_avg\", \"udps_bwd_bk_rate_avg\", \"udps_subflow_fwd_pkts\", \"udps_subflow_bwd_pkts\", \"udps_subflow_bwd_bytes\", \"udps_init_fwd_win_bytes\", \"udps_init_bwd_win_bytes\", \"udps_fwd_act_data_pkts\", \"udps_fwd_seg_size_min\", \"udps_active_mean\", \"udps_active_std\", \"udps_active_max\", \"udps_active_min\", \"udps_idle_mean\", \"udps_idle_std\", \"udps_idle_max\", \"udps_idle_min\", \"bidirectional_packets\"]",
    "model_id": "model_123",
    "reconstruction_error": 0.83,
    "comparison_metric": "HSE",
    "tf_version": "v0.2.1",
    "nfstream_version": "v0.6.0",
    "timestamp": 1912390190290
  }
}

```

Figure 6 - HSPF Outbound Data.

⁵ <https://www.nfstream.org/>

6.5. Mapping of AI-driven Federated Anomaly Detection Assets to HLA

Figure 7 - Mapping of AI-driven federated anomaly detection assets to RIGOUROUS's HLA.

As illustrated in Figure 7, the AI-driven federated anomaly detection assets implement the functionalities of the “privacy-preserving federated AI anomaly detection” functional block, providing both “anomaly detection” and “federated training” services. For anomaly detection service, the assets analyse security data collected by the Data Monitoring functional block from managed entities within the domain. Once an anomaly is detected, the AI-driven Decision (AID) functional block is alerted, providing necessary information that aids in ascertaining the type of cybersecurity threat or intrusion responsible for the anomaly. The federated training service facilitates a cross-domain FL-based collaborative training of the DL models incorporated within the anomaly detection assets.

7 AI-DRIVEN ATTACK COGNITIVE DECISION MAKING, ORCHESTRATION, AND MANAGEMENT

7.1. Introduction

In the ever-evolving landscape of cybersecurity, delving into the intricacies of developing an AI-driven module tasked with automated decision-making for threat mitigation in a case-by-case methodology, takes centre stage. As cyber threats become more sophisticated, traditional rule-based systems prove inadequate in addressing the multifaceted nature of these challenges. This undertaking aims to explore and implement advanced strategies that ensure swift and effective mitigation, considering an array of threats and network operating conditions.

The focal point of this Chapter is the development of AI algorithms through supervised learning. These algorithms will decode the complexities of threat handling based on multidimensional datasets, constructing comprehensive plans that may involve various steps tailored to the specifics of each threat. Leveraging and extending the capabilities of the Cyber-Physical Correlator, which integrates behavioural information, events, and network data from diverse sources, this task merges rules-based systems and machine learning approaches for real-time anomaly detection, intrusion pattern recognition, and root cause analysis.

To ensure the robustness and effectiveness of the AI algorithms, a meticulous experimental design plan was devised. This plan outlines the properties of the training data and procedures, including but not limited to cross-validation, utilisation of larger datasets, regularisation, and model assembly, with a keen focus on preventing AI training bias and overfitting.

The overarching goal of this Chapter is the research and development of a security risk assessment framework for the deployed 6G network orchestration. This Framework comprises of Threat Risk Assessor (TRA) Functional block. The TRA examines threat information and gathers vulnerability characteristics pertaining to targeted assets or resources, encompassing various elements such as end-user devices, applications, IoT devices, and cloud or network resources. It functions as a co-processor to AID, relying on a risk-based threat assessment formula: $RISK\ SCORE = THREAT * \{VULNERABILITY * TRUST\}$. Primarily serving external consumers, especially AI decision-making entities, this service necessitates prior knowledge of existing or potential vulnerabilities linked to specified assets or resources. It utilizes data from both internal management/data services and external repositories, including the NIST National Vulnerability Database and the MITRE Common Vulnerability & Exposure. The TRA is responsible for evaluating the risk level associated with potential threats, acquiring crucial threat identification and threat type information from AID. Operating with an internal risk matrix, it integrates contextual mitigation factors from external services such as the Zero Trust Model (ZTM). A high-level architecture of the discussed modules is shown in Figure 8, with more details on the architecture to be discussed in the last subsection of the chapter.

Figure 8 - Cognitive Decision, Orchestration, and Security Management.

7.2. Cyber-Physical Correlator

7.2.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

In detecting attacks in an IoT network, a Network Intrusion Detection System (NIDS) is proposed to serve as additional line of defence after access control systems, antivirus, and firewalls for connected IoT devices [22]. A NIDS is an IDS system that capitalizes on network behaviour to work effectively by examining data exchanged within the network. A network-based IDS is deployed to detect intrusions in network data over network connections and protect all network nodes. There are two types of NIDN: Anomaly/ML based and Signature based.

Anomaly-Based

An anomaly-based IDS is able to determine if a behaviour is normal or an attack without following hard coded rules. The generality of this technique makes it extremely hard for intruders to avoid. Additionally, compared to the signature-based technique, the anomaly-based technique can detect new attacks that have not been previously known (day zero attacks). Nevertheless, the technique has the drawback of having high-false positive rates, which makes working in some cases difficult for it.

Signature Based

A signature-based IDS is linked with a specific intrusive exploit [23]. An antivirus program is the most common signature-based technique software, which has the task of scanning the signatures of all data downloaded or traversing through the network on a device.

Since securing the cyber infrastructure is of paramount importance for many organizations, network intrusion detection techniques have been used and are still being studied in many recent studies. Many studies are still utilizing traditional and well-known datasets that have existed for over 15 years, like KDD99 [24] and NLS-KDD [25] datasets. These datasets were very important for intrusion detection at their age, but they are unable to meet present-day requirements. In the study of Almseidin et al. [26], the focus was on evaluating various machine learning classifiers for false positive and false negative performance using the KDD99 dataset. However, the dataset is an outdated one. Similarly, Obeidat et al. [27], investigated the accuracy performance of some ML

classifiers for attack detection on the dataset using the KDD99 dataset. In the work of Rajadurai and Gandhi [28], a stack ensemble learner was evaluated using the NLS-KDD dataset for anomaly detection. Although all the above-listed studies are recent, they all utilized datasets that do not have IoT network traces.

In the context of RIGOUROUS, we will enhance our Cyber-Physical Correlator by adding Network Intrusion detection capabilities apart from already using physical detection capabilities like motion detection and human/object detection from the camera stream. In order to train the model, we will use two well-known and recently developed datasets, namely: UNSW-NB15 and Edge-IIoTset.

UNSW-NB15 [29] has nine types of modern attack types and new patterns of normal traffic, and it contains 49 attributes that comprise the flow based between hosts and the network packets inspection to discriminate between the observations, either normal or abnormal.

Edge-IIoTset [30] can be used by machine learning-based intrusion detection systems in two different modes, namely, centralized and federated learning. Specifically, the proposed testbed is organized into seven layers, including, Cloud Computing Layer, Network Functions Virtualization Layer, Blockchain Network Layer, Fog Computing Layer, Software-Defined Networking Layer, Edge Computing Layer, and IoT and IIoT Perception Layer.

7.2.2. Asset Description

Cyber Physical Correlator can identify anomalies by understanding changes in the distribution of transmitted data. One big advantage of the tool is that it can correlate events from heterogeneous sources. So, if an abnormal value is reported by one sensor and after a while another sensor sends an anomalous value, the two events can be correlated, and the user will be informed for a possible serious incident instead of just anomalous events from two sensors. Cyber Physical Correlator can contribute to the physical security of the installation too, by consuming messages from CCTV cameras, motion sensors, flame detectors etc. For the RIGOUROUS project, the main focus will be to use Cyber Physical Correlator in order to detect intrusions in the computer network. In order to train the tool, we will use UNSW-NB 15 [29] and Edge IIoTSET [30] datasets. Cyber Physical Correlator will be able to detect attacks in the network like DoS/DDoS attacks, Information gathering, Man in the middle attacks, Injection attacks, and Malware attacks. As mentioned, Correlator can correlate anomalies in the network with abnormal situations detected by sensors in the field and in that way to have better accuracy and decrease false alerts.

Figure 9 shows the general architecture of the solution. The connected devices send messages to a Kafka broker. Then, the messages are consumed, and the information is stored in a database. Correlator reads the information and makes predictions using Machine Learning algorithms. In case an anomaly is detected, the user is informed by an alert message that is shown in the dashboard.

Figure 9 - Functional architecture of Cyber-Physical Correlator.

7.3. AI-driven Decision Engine

7.3.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

The advancement of AI technology has led to the rapid evolution of attack methods, rendering some existing detection methods less effective over time, despite their continuing attractiveness. Most of the available methods are rooted in academic settings and make certain assumptions that need to be considered when applying them in practical scenarios. AI-powered threats, such as targeted attacks, adaptive attacks and deep locker, are emerging attacks that utilize AI capabilities to launch various types of assaults on the system [1][31]. Conventional adversarial attacks are typically easier to detect since the attack patterns rely on algorithms. However, more recent attacks make use of AI features, such as machine learning and deep learning, to make malware more evasive and extensive. Moreover, the integration of AI techniques with automation can make the malware more scalable and capable of attacking targets without human intervention [31].

The evolving nature of the threats has become increasingly complex, prompting the need for the integration of ML techniques to enhance security measures. The utilization of machine learning is crucial for staying ahead of sophisticated adversaries. Classification techniques can be used to

design decision engines such as decision trees [32], IntrudTree [33], BehavDT [34], Ripple Down Rule learner (RIDOR) [35], Repeated Incremental Pruning to Produce Error Reduction (RIPPER) [36], etc. However, solely relying on classification models can result in false positives and false negatives that can result in decisions based on false threats or decisions that do not mitigate threats. To address this problem, association-based decision rules can be generated using the If-Then pattern along with the confidence value. Common association rule learning techniques such as AIS [37], Apriori [38], FP-Tree [39], RARM [40], Eclat [41], ABC-RuleMiner [42], etc. can be used. In the context of RIGOROUS, we will enhance our AI-driven decision engine by integrating the advanced ML techniques along with the confidence values that would be fed by TRA, thus providing it with the enhanced capability of prioritizing the threats. This would not only enhance the capabilities of the machine learning techniques as compared to stagnant if-else decisions but also introduce capability of making adaptive decisions based on the risk matrix and threat severity value.

7.3.2. Asset Description

AI-driven Decision Engine can take decisions by applying ML algorithms and models. One big advantage of the tool is that it can identify and relate to the threats and makes decisions based on the severity matrix that it calculates. So, if a threat is reported to have a more probable score with a higher risk index, it can prioritize it based on the risk index value it calculates. This methodology that uses AI-driven decision-making process prioritizes the threats based on risk levels provided by the TRA functional block, enabling informed decision-making for the AI-driven orchestrator. Furthermore, a root analysis is introduced for handling unexpected cyber-attacks. Figure 10 and Figure 11 show a visual representation of the AI-driven Decision Engine's architecture, its inputs and outputs along with its data types.

Figure 10 - Functional Architecture - AI-driven Decision-Making FB Input & Output Data Interfaces Abstract FB Architecture.

Figure 11 represents a visual representation of the functional block architecture, which includes its inputs, and Outputs, as well as the data requirements needed to be fully operational.

• AID Functional Block – Architecture Design-Development

Actual Main SAE Data Inputs

- Input In1 - Physical Correlator Data
- Input In2 - Federated AI Anomaly Detection Data
- Input In3 - Federated AI Anomaly Detection Data

Adaptive Feedback Data Inputs

- Input In4 - Adaptive Feedback DS
- Input In5 - Adaptive Feedback ZTM
- Input In6 - Adaptive Feedback TRA

Data Outputs

- Output Out7 TRA
- Output Out8 ZTM
- Output Out9 OS

Data Sets Requirements

- Datasheet or JSON Format – Data Communication Protocol for each FB
- SAE and AID Protocol Information, when SAE produces the output results (e.g MQTT, TCP-IP) for the exchange of information

Figure 2. AI-driven Decision Making FB - Input & Output Data Interfaces - Abstract FB Architecture

Figure 11 - AID FB Requirements Data I/Os - Interfaces.

The choice of algorithm also depends on the specific characteristics of the data and the nature of the cyber threats that will be used based on the specific dataset. Various datasets will be used to deploy different types of cyber-attacks. Table 4 illustrates the AI/ML Techniques, datasets, ML model's inputs and outputs that will be used for the AI-driven Decision Engine. The envisioned AI/ML models may receive inputs from Federated AI Anomaly Detection (FED AI), Physical Correlator (PC) and/or MTD based Robust AI (MTD) functional blocks.

Table 4 - AI/ML techniques for AID functional block.

AI/ML Technique(s)	Dataset(s)	ML Model's Inputs	ML Model's Output
Reinforcement Learning (RL) algorithm, CNN, FL, MLP	Gas Pipeline (public) WUSTL-IIoT (public)	FED AI, PC, MTD	MultiClass Classification 0-Normal i (>0)-Attack Class
Support Vector Machines (SVMs), CNN, FL, MLP	5G-NIDD (public), vCDN_EDoS,	FED AI, PC, MTD	Binary Classification 0-Normal 1-Anomaly (requires further Attack Classification)
DL (RNN, CNN, GNN)	vCDN_EDoS	FED AI, PC, MTD	Binary Classification 0-Normal 1-Anomaly (requires further Attack Classification)

AI/ML Technique(s)	Dataset(s)	ML Model's Inputs	ML Model's Output
Deep Autoencoder, MLP, FL	ToN-IoT (public) 5G-NIDD (public)	FED AI, PC, MTD	Binary Classification 0-Normal 1-Attack (requires further Attack Classification)
Neural Networks (NN), K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN)	CIC IDS2017 CSE-CIC-IDS2018	FED AI, PC, MTD	Binary Classification 0-Normal 1-Malicious (requires further Attack Classification)

7.4. Zero-Touch Device Bootstrapping

7.4.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

Device bootstrapping describes a process of connecting a device to a network for authentication and secure connection setup. The IETF draft on “Secure IoT Bootstrapping” [43] provides a great overview of the SOTA mechanisms in place, e.g., Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP) [44] or Wi-Fi Protected Setup (WPS) push button [45] as well as a good categorization into managed methods, peer to peer and ad-hoc methods, opportunistic and leap-of-faith methods as well as hybrid methods. The bootstrapping methods depend on whether the IoT devices are preconfigured with credentials or have the capability for out-of-band control signalling, which depends on several factors like the device capabilities, processing power and the UI offered by the device.

For the RIGOUROUS project, the managed methods with respect to the 3GPP defined bootstrapping features like General Bootstrapping Architecture (GBA), Battery Efficient Security for very low throughput Machine Type Communication (MTC) devices (BEST) and Authentication and Key Management for Applications (AKMA) based on 3GPP credentials in the 5GS play a significant role considering the current development towards 6G. The credential provisioning during the bootstrapping procedure without interaction is a key aspect, considering the large number of devices that may be deployed or located in remote locations or unreachable parts of bigger products for example an industrial production machine, a car etc. Further, it is not only required that the IoT devices are provisioned with credentials and authenticated, also the applications running on the IoT device must be genuine. Modern operating systems for mobile devices allow the installation of virus scanners and can also support trusted computing platforms in some sense, but for IoT devices those are too complex considering the purpose, low-cost requirements, and potentially long battery life goals.

So far despite there are several attempts to provide bootstrapping for a large amount of IoT devices with different capabilities, there is no major specification that gained relevance in the market. The provisioning of credentials during the bootstrapping for varied types of devices need to be solved in a general way with a zero-touch process in order to integrate as many IoT devices to the system of the RIGOUROUS project. The devices need to have a method to verify a genuine application considering the computation power, memory, and operating system constraints. If a large number of IoT devices are compromised with a malicious software package, then different attack types from creating a botnet towards performing a DDoS attack on a specific target are possible. Therefore, the IoT device should be also able to verify the installed applications and whether they map to the security requirements from the network side, especially if the IoT device has to update or further install applications for a particular service.

7.4.2. Asset Description

The zero-touch device bootstrapping asset describes how the IoT devices can connect to a network for authentication and secure connection setup. The bootstrapping procedure should consider verifiable secure identification with privacy preservation and pseudonymization (i.e., with digital identifiers such as., decentralized identifiers/self-sovereign identifiers), and further it involves the provisioning of the long-term credentials used to authenticate and authorize the access to the network services over 6G. The zero-touch bootstrapping belongs to the asset enabling the cognitive security decision-making, orchestration and management services, comprising an AI-driven physical correlator for allowing a more comprehensive assessment of cybersecurity threats.

The details of the asset description are provided in Section 5.2 of deliverable D3.1, including the functional architecture (see Section 5.2.1.1) of the affected functions and the detailed call flows (Section 5.2.3.1).

7.5. Trusted Application Onboarding

7.5.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

The identification and authentication of the end-user/user equipment (UE) requesting a network access or resource is a key aspect that plays a significant role in the network access control, where in the 5G System (5GS) in few scenarios (i.e., NPN onboarding) allows UE to request registration with network access identifier (NAI of form username@realm) which skips the username part or uses a static keyword 'anonymous' (e.g. for privacy) which is termed as anonymous Subscription Concealed Identifier (SUCI) [46], this practise has significant limitation that authentication server needs to implement only one authentication method (e.g., EAP-TLS) only then this identification method would work else if the authentication server implements more than one authentication method and handles more than one type of devices/UEs which relies on different authentication methods then identification of the UEs is not feasible and also skipping of username/having static anonymous keyword for the NAI can allow malicious operations such as the launch of DDoS over the network, as the network receiving only a meaningful realm can only route the authentication

request (related to the registration) to the right authentication server, but the authentication server cannot select any credentials/authentication method or cannot identify the UE leading to multiple message exchange with the malicious UE and identification of malicious UE after several round trips. As millions of devices are expected to connect with a 6G System (6GS), any UE onboarding method should consider identification with anonymization and privacy preservation as key requirements.

7.5.2. Asset Description

The Trusted Application Onboarding asset describes how to avoid malicious applications being installed in IoT devices and taking over the resources granted for genuine applications. Malicious applications could be installed on a multitude of devices like video cameras to form e.g. a botnet for distributed denial of service (DDoS) attacks, without the knowledge of the device owners. The Trusted Application Onboarding asset validates the applications installed on a device with received information from the network so that they can be identified as malicious or as spoofing genuine applications. The asset belongs to the cognitive security decision-making, orchestration, and management services, which comprises an AI-driven decision-making service that may take information about the applications on the devices into account.

The details of the asset description are provided in Section 5.2 of deliverable D3.1, including the functional architecture (see Section 5.2.1.2) of the affected functions and the detailed call flows (Section 5.2.3.2).

7.6. Trust evaluation and Trust enabler service framework

7.6.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

According to NIST.SP.800-207 [47], Zero Trust is a cybersecurity paradigm focused on resource protection and the principle that trust is never granted implicitly but must be continually evaluated. Zero trust security (ZTS) models assume that an attacker is present in the environment, and continually analyses and evaluates the risks to the assets and business functions and enacts protections to mitigate the identified risks. In zero trust, the protection usually involves minimizing access to resources (such as data, compute resources, applications/services) to only those subjects and assets identified as needing access as well as continually authenticating and authorizing the identity and security posture of each access request. Zero trust provides a collection of concepts and ideas designed to minimize uncertainty in enforcing accurate, least privilege per-request access decisions in information systems and services in the face of a network viewed as compromised. Some of the key tenets of ZTS include (i) Consideration of all data sources and computing services as resources; (ii) Applying security for all communication regardless of network location; (iii) Granting of access to an individual resource on a per-session basis; (iv) Determination of access to resources need based on dynamic policy – including the observable state of identity, application/service and the requesting asset, can include other behavioural and environmental attributes; (v) Monitoring and measuring the integrity and security posture of all owned and associated assets; (vi) Resource authentication and authorization per access; and (vii) Collection of

information related to the current state of assets, network infrastructure and communication to improve the associated security posture. The 5G communication network security currently adapts most of the tenets of ZTS but does not support part of tenet iv, v and vii which are very essential to enable trusted communication and reliable service.

The 6GS is expected to involve multiple stakeholders such as millions of devices, different network products, applications, and vertical service providers, where the heterogeneity and varied network deployment options need to expect threats such as insider attacks, cyber-attack, botnets, errors due to configuration issues etc., and should be designed to ensure seamless and trusted service in addition to authentication, authorization, and secure communication. The trust of any party such as network function, application function or end user device cannot be assumed to be static and intact throughout its lifetime despite all default security configuration. The Zero trust security is a paramount requirement to be adopted for 6GS and so, RIGOROUS will analyse, identify, and describe methods to offer trust service in 6G to adopt ZTS (i.e., to enable a transition from network defence towards a more proactive in-advance security to be in place to combat the security threats if they occur due to any malicious operations or compromised network functionalities). The 6G ZTS adaptation methodology will describe the proposed trust service which can enable continuous trust validation (i.e., monitoring the state) and minimization of impacts (i.e., if any security breach occurs prevention of threat lateral movement), where the trust service will consider various factors including behavioural/environmental attributes, monitoring/measuring the integrity or security posture of the involved function or entity in the communication system etc., Further, if any network function or application function is evaluated to have less trust or is under threat simply terminating them would impact all the ongoing service, therefore the trust service describes methods to ensure seamless service even if any of the involved network/application function is compromised. 6GS will encompass various business models involving home network and/or 3rd party service provider having service level agreement (SLA) to offer service through localized networks or different network service provider(s) as part of long term or short-term subscriptions. In such scenarios, it is very essential for the home network and/or the 3rd party service provider to know, if the serving network provides all service requested by the user (based on the subscription) or if the serving network denies some or whole of the service requested by the user due to resource limitation or due to any malicious behaviour. Therefore, beyond SOTA will consider potential methods to ensure trustworthiness (such as leveraging permissioned distributed ledger technology to report any service failure/rejection) to handle the serving network trust and service offering reliability related to roaming services. As millions of devices are expected to be connected with 6GS, beyond SOTA will consider verifiable secure identification with privacy preservation and anonymization (i.e., with digital identifiers such as., decentralized identifiers/self-sovereign identifiers) for the UE onboarding related to non-public network (NPN) and other temporary services (e.g., network as a service) over 6GS.

7.6.2. Asset Description

The Trust evaluation and enabler service asset described in Section 6 of deliverable D3.1, provides a set of functionalities and services for abnormal behaviour-based security evaluation and monitoring and to use gained insight(s) for security policy generation and fine-grained access control enforcement.

The trust evaluation and enabler service might apply AI algorithms for trust related evaluation analytics and predictions. The Trust evaluation and enabler service asset provides information regarding the level of risk (e.g., trust scores) associated to the entities in the network (i.e., end-device, RAN or core NF) considering the identified cyber threats as inputs to the AI-Driven Decision Making (AID) functional block for respective security decisions.

For decision (and corresponding mitigation) purposes in the network, the Trust evaluation and enabler service plays a significant role, encompassing the following functionalities:

- **Evaluation of Trustworthiness:** Trust evaluation and enabler service function (TESF) evaluates the trustworthiness of any target in the network, where a target will be a network node/function in the Core, RAN, end-user device(s) (e.g., UEs), application function etc. The TESF will provide the trust data notifications to a set of authorized trust service consumers (i.e., network node(s) / function(s) in the core or management domain) by means of subscribe/unsubscribe and notification service(s).
- **Data Collection:** Event based Direct data collection and Indirect Data (via Operations, Administration, and Management (OAM)) collection and Trust evaluation.
- **Coordination with Security Orchestrator for policy enforcement:** Trust service consumer(s) based on the trust data notifications (e.g., security and trust evaluation results) namely the security Orchestrator can configure security policies to enable invocation of recommended actions to ensure trusted services and service continuation.

The abovementioned functionalities are further elaborated in Section 6 of deliverable D3.1, covering component design and primary workflow.

7.7. Mapping of AI-driven Attack Cognitive Decision Making, Orchestration, and Management Assets to HLA

This comprehensive framework is built upon a critical component known as the Cognitive Decision, Orchestration, and Management (CDOM) Plane, which functions as the central hub for intelligent decision-making and effective response to cyber threats. The current section is focusing on the mapping of AI-driven Attack CDOM assets to HLA as shown in Figure 12. Furthermore, this section analyses the steps required for the CDOM sub-system to communicate with the Security Analytics Engine SAE sub-system but also with AI-driven Response Mitigation sub-system of the RIGOUROUS System Architecture.

As data traverses through various layers of the 6G network infrastructure, automated AI Data Analytics and Monitoring Services come into play. The TRA is informed by the AI-driven federated anomaly detection, providing a precise assessment of attack risk levels.

Figure 12 - Reactive Flow RIGOUROUS System Architecture Functional Blocks Diagram.

This data communication flow undergoes several crucial steps:

Step 1-Data Monitoring (DM): Operating within the Monitoring & Analytics Plane, DM scrutinizes data processing performance and security across the multi-domain network and layers. It verifies the effectiveness of security policies and their validation.

Step 2-Data Services (DS): DS collates data from DM based on service and security types. It serves as the input for the AID Functional Block, supplying Network Topology information and other pertinent data for actuation if required. Additionally, DS furnishes critical Security Information and Event Management processed within the 6G network.

Step 3-Privacy Preserving Sharing ICT: This step ensures secure and confidential data management by examining access safety and privacy policies. It facilitates trustworthy data privacy, safeguarding against unauthorized access and potential data compromise.

Step 4-AI-driven Cyber Physical Correlator: Providing crucial AI-derived physical parameters and data, this block serves both DS and the AID Functional Block. It furnishes information such as network traffic, numerical data flow, and IP source channel data.

Step 5-Federated AI Anomaly Detection: This component delivers additional input to the AID Functional Block, working in tandem with the AI-Driven Cyber Physical Correlator to enhance AI Data Analytics and security insights. The AI-driven Federated Anomaly Detection detects and classifies the type of cyber-attacks, intrusions, and anomalies.

As the AID mechanism processes a multitude of inputs, its primary operations involve self-learning and adaptation. This encompasses both AI-Processed Data and AI Physical Data, along with adaptive feedback. When a threat is identified and classified, the AID Functional Block immediately triggers a tailored response-mitigation plan, effectively activating a security solution. Furthermore, it communicates with the Security Orchestrator to initiate additional security measures.

AI-driven Cognitive, Decision, Orchestration, and Management (CDOM) - primary assets:

1. **Intelligent Decision Making:** The CDOM Plane aims to leverage the power of AI to make informed decisions regarding threat identification, classification, and response.
2. **Orchestration and Coordination:** It is imperative to orchestrate various security measures cohesively. The CDOM Plane seeks to streamline the integration of AI-driven assets and ensure seamless cooperation among different security components.
3. **Efficient Management of Security Response:** The objective of the CDOM plane is to expedite and enhance the efficiency of security operations by leveraging artificial intelligence and data from a diverse range of sources.

Technological Operations:

The CDOM Plane operates through a cycle of continuous analysis, decision-making, and response:

- **Data Input and Analysis:** The CDOM plane ingests data from various sources, including the AI-driven Security Analytics Engine (SAE), Federated AI Anomaly Detection, AI-Driven Cyber-Physical Correlator, TRA and ZTM.
- **AI-Driven Decision Making:** This phase involves the utilization of advanced AI models to process incoming data and make informed decisions regarding threat severity and appropriate response strategies.
- **Orchestration and Coordination:** The CDOM Plane orchestrates security measures based on the decisions made, ensuring a synchronized response to mitigate threats effectively.
- **Response Implementation:** The security plan, mitigation strategies and responses are executed promptly, safeguarding the system from potential risks.

In essence, the CDOM Plane stands as a testament to the transformative power of AI in cybersecurity, revolutionizing the way organizations combat cyber threats. Through intelligent decision-making, precise orchestration, and efficient management, it marks a significant leap forward in securing digital landscapes.

The following mapping table (see Table 5) indicates the attacks-anomalies-intrusions detected by each partner, as an input to the AID functional block, including the AI/ML techniques and datasets that will be used.

Table 5 - AI-driven Attack Cognitive Decision making, Orchestration, and Management (CDOM) Assets to HLA - Mapping Table.

Partner	Asset	Attacks / Intrusions/ Anomalies Considered	AI/ML Technique(s)	Dataset(s)	AI/ML Model's Input	AI/ML Model Detection Output	AI/ML Model Classification Output Binary Class or Multi-Class
OULOU	Privacy-preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector	-Cyber-attacks against IIoT <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DoS • Reconnaissance • Command injection • Backdoor attack 	DL (MLP, CNN), FL, Continual Learning	GAS PIPELINE (public) WUSTL-IIoT (public)	MODBUS Network traffic features from a gas pipeline industrial control system	Multi-class classification: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0 - Normal • 1 (i>0) - Attack class 	Multi-class classification: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0 - Normal • 1 (i>0) - Attack class
		-5G-network intrusion detection <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network-layer DoS/DDoS • Application-layer DoS/DDoS 		5G-NIDD (public)	Network flow features	Binary classification <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0 - Normal • 1 - Attack 	Binary classification <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0 - Normal • 1 - Attack
OULOU	AI-powered EDoS Mitigator	-App-layer DDoS attacks that can reshape to EDoS	DL (RNN, CNN, GNN), Transfer learning	vCDN EDoS	Observed resource usage and service performance metrics values of previous w time steps	The future metrics values forecasted for the next time step	Metrics at time step t are flagged as anomalous if the prediction error is above a given threshold. Thus, the output of the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator is: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0 - Normal • 1 - Anomaly
UMU	Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User-plane attacks against IoT environments (backdoor, injection, man-in-the-middle, DoS/DDoS, password, scanning, ransomware, XSS) • User plane attacks against 5G networks (network and application-layer DoS/DDoS) • Control-plane attacks against 5G core network (PFCP-based attacks, replay attacks, malformed packet attacks) 	Deep Autoencoder, MLP, FL	ToN-IoT (public) 5G-NIDD (public) Own dataset for CP attacks (not ready yet)	Network traffic features from monitoring probes deployed in the infrastructure	Multi-class classification (benign or specific type of attack)	Multi-class classification (benign or specific type of attack)

Partner	Asset	Attacks / Intrusions/ Anomalies Considered	AI/ML Technique(s)	Dataset(s)	AI/ML Model's Input	AI/ML Model Detection Output	AI/ML Model Classification Output Binary Class or Multi-Class
ONE	Holistic Security and Privacy Framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dataset: DoS Hulk, PortScan, DDoS, DoS, GoldenEye, FTP-Patator, SSH-Patator, DoS Slowloris, DoS Slowhttptest, Bot, Web Attack - Brute Force, Web Attack - XSS, Infiltration, Web Attack - SQL Injection, Heartbleed; Simulated: DDoS, Port Scan, Web Attack - Brute Force, Web Attack - SQL Injection; 	Auto-Encoder (Conventional and Convolutional)	CIC-IDS2017 CSE-CIC-IDS2018	Network flow features	Network flow features	Binary classification: 0 - Normal 1 - Malicious
WINGS	Cyber Physical Correlator	DoS/DDoS attacks, Information gathering, Man in the middle attacks, Injection attacks, Malware attacks	Decision Trees Random Forest Neural Networks	UNSW-NB15 Edge-IIoTset	Network flow features	Multi-class classification: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0 - Normal i (i>0) - Attack class 	Multi-class classification: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0 - Normal i (i>0) - Attack class

8 AI-DRIVEN SECURITY RESPONSE-MITIGATION

8.1. Introduction

In recent years, a high proliferation of different types of malware and ransomware has been observed. In addition, cyberattacks upgrade very quickly and are able to cause more and more serious damage to infrastructure, since they depend very much on software. This has made traditional signature-based detection solutions, upon which most common antivirus software is based, obsolete. It is therefore increasingly necessary to use machine-learning solutions that are able to detect anomalies and attacks without relying on hard-coded rules, which cannot cover all cyber threats, as the latter are created at an ever-faster pace. These solutions are based on ML algorithms that can automatically analyse different types of files, as well as the packets transmitted in the network to detect abnormal conditions that may be caused by an attack.

The most common malware detection procedures are the following:

- Hashes file calculation: Hash value algorithms are algorithms that can produce a unique, fixed-length string (the hash value) for any piece of data. Hashes values are non-reversible, which means that given the hash value, someone cannot reproduce the file. Hash values enable to compare files without opening them. So, we can know if a file is malicious if its hash value is equal with the one of a known malware.
- System monitoring: System monitoring can be used for attack detection by detecting abnormal operations of the system. for example, an unusual increase in central processing unit (CPU) cycles or an increased hard drive write activity may indicate that the system is under attack.
- Network monitoring: Network monitoring is the process that continuously monitors the network in order to detect anomalies like unexpected traffic, unknown devices and uncharacteristic application usage.

8.2. AI-powered EDoS Mitigator

8.2.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

Auto-scaling is a key life cycle management operation of network slices, allowing to dynamically expand or contract the capacity of a network slice instance to accommodate resources to slice workload to meet the performance needs. However, the auto-scaling capability is a double-edged sword that can reshape an undetected DDoS attack into an EDoS attack, inflicting serious economic damages to service provider due to the increased elastic usage of resources [48][49]. Hence, providing reliable dynamic resource provisioning that is EDoS attack aware is paramount to enable profitable beyond 5G services. Achieving this goal is challenging due to the growing trend toward more stealthier DDoS attacks that are aiming at the application layer rather than the network layer. Despite the extensive work that has been undertaken to counteract DDoS attacks, the stealthy application-layer DDoS issue is far from being addressed, and even less in B5G slicing environment. Existing solutions have a number of limitations, which hampers their effectiveness and efficiency [48][49]. The total isolation among slices promoted by resource isolation-based

approaches (e.g., [50]) may result in over-provisioning of resources or may not be possible to achieve due to lack of strong hardware isolation in the emerging cloud-native platforms [2]. By imitating legitimate traffic, application-layer DDoS attacks can escape detection by network traffic analysis-based solutions (e.g., [51], [52]) Using resource scaling as a mitigation strategy by resource allocation-based methods (e.g., [53]) grows the risk of revamping an undetected application-layer DDoS attack into an EDoS attack [54]. The recent anomaly detection approaches (e.g., [2], [55], [56]) that leverage the potential of Deep Learning (DL) to recognize abnormal behaviour based on anomalies detected in service performance and/or resource usage metrics are a promising direction to tackle EDoS attack. However, existing anomaly detection methods only consider temporal correlations between metrics and/or assume that sufficient amount of historical data is available for training the DL models to learn normal behaviour.

Driven by the aforementioned limitations of DL-based anomaly detection approaches and the limited research work tackling the EDoS issue in 5G network slicing, we propose in RIGUROUS a novel framework that aims to proactively mitigate EDoS attacks against network slicing by intelligently safeguarding from malicious resource scaling requests caused by stealthy application-layer DDoS attacks. The framework capitalizes on the potential of emerging DL techniques to capture the spatio-temporal dependencies to accurately discriminate malicious behaviour, and leverages the concept of Transfer Learning to effectively defeat EDoS attacks in newly deployed slices.

8.2.2. Asset Description

The AI-powered EDoS Mitigator is capable of proactively mitigating EDoS attacks by adopting a DL-powered forecasting-based approach for detecting malicious scaling requests caused by application-layer DDoS attacks. As depicted in Figure 13, the resource usage and service performance metrics are collected from the slice's Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) by a monitoring system. Once a horizontal scaling-in request (i.e., adding VNF replica instance) is triggered at the Auto-Scaling Module, the request is first assessed by the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator to decide about the legitimacy or maliciousness of the observed resource usage and performance metrics of the slice's virtual network function (VNF). Trained to recognize a normal behaviour of a VNF, the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator will detect anomalous resource usage and service performance metrics of a VNF by comparing the observed metrics to the predicted ones. If the deviation between the actual and predicted values is above a given threshold, the VNF's behaviour is flagged as anomalous and the scaling request as malicious.

Figure 13 - Functional architecture of AI-powered EDoS Mitigator asset.

The AI-powered EDoS Mitigator incorporates a hybrid DL model that combines the advantages of different deep neural network algorithms to provide both feature extraction and forecasting capabilities. Specifically, CNN, Graph Attention (GAT) and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) algorithms are used to extract relevant local features, spatial correlations and time dependencies among VNF’s metrics, respectively, and MLP algorithm is utilized for enabling forecasting capability. Table 6 provides a summary about ML techniques to be used to build the anomaly detection model incorporated in AI-powered EDoS Mitigator, the inputs and outputs to the ML model, as well as the dataset used to train and test the model.

Table 6 - Summary of details related to ML model incorporated in AI-powered EDoS Mitigator asset.

AI/ML Technique(s)	Dataset(s)	ML Model’s Inputs	ML Model’s Output
- Hybrid DL (CNN, GAT, GRU, MLP) - Transfer Learning	vCDN_EDoS ⁶	The observed resource usage and service performance metrics values of previous w time steps.	The future values forecasted for the next time step. The metrics at time step t are flagged as anomalous if the prediction error is above a given threshold.

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/record/8111592>

8.3. Dynamic and Automated Service Composition

8.3.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

In recent years we have witnessed the enormous impact that Internet of Things has in many fields such as manufacturing, transportation, health, public sector but also in everyday life as well. The vast amount of different types of devices that can be connected to the IoT apart from possibilities, they also create some challenges. One of the most important challenges that comes with IoT is interoperability since not all devices are compatible with each other. Interoperability of IoT devices has been the subject of many studies. In [57], authors propose a context-based service composition method which use OWL to build the ontology of context in IoT environment. In [58], researchers propose a middleware approach that uses a decentralized coordination mechanism to monitor the component services with few resources efficiently. In [59], a probabilistic approach is proposed in order to formally describe and analyse the reliability and cost-related properties of the service composition in IoT. In [60], researchers propose a framework for assessing the reputation of a set of services as a measure for the suitability of such services in coping with a given task.

However, most of the studies that have dealt with the subject do not take protection and trust management into account. In the context of RIGOUROUS, we will develop Dynamic Automated Service Composition which can detect and propose solutions for cases where composition requirements are not satisfied and simultaneously provides management of trust in order to be able to resist malicious attacks.

8.3.2. Asset Description

Dynamic automated service composition is a service that can detect and resolve the interconnection problems among components that are attempting to interoperate. The interconnection problems may be due to different communication protocols that are used by the different components, encoding mismatches, notation mismatches, mismatches in units etc. When a mismatch is detected, Dynamic automated service composition suggests some conversions to overcome the issue. Recommendations may involve changes to the source code or changes in the container. Additionally, an ontology can be used for the mismatch identification. Finally, the service can use machine learning algorithms to classify the causes of the problems in different categories. Dynamic automated service composition uses interfaces to connect with Digital Twin and Response-Mitigation. Digital Twin provides simulation of different software and hardware components that interact with each other, and Dynamic automated service composition analyses if there are interconnection problems. In case of interoperability issues, the service proposes solutions via Response-Mitigation component.

8.4. AI-driven Algorithm for Risk Management and Mitigation Provision

8.4.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

6G will take the 5G function of a software-controlled network/cloud and advance it into a highly intelligent network, revolutionizing wireless networks from connected things to “connected intelligence” [61]. Therefore, service provision for extreme requirements with complex 6G networks requires sophisticated security mechanisms [62]. The security systems designed for 5G that are based on the concepts of SDN and NFV should be upgraded to accommodate the security demands in 6G. The end-to-end security design leveraging AI techniques are indispensable to autonomously identify and respond to potential threats based on network anomalies rather than other cryptographic methods [63]. AI capabilities can help intelligently automate repetitive and manual cybersecurity tasks, including cybersecurity controls and control functions [64][65]. Using AI in this way, leads to improved efficiency and effectiveness in using cyber controls, along with controls process simplification, enhanced control visibility and control-related cost reduction [66][67].

In the context of RIGOUROUS, a mitigation framework that allows to prioritize threats, come up with a mitigation plan and create a complete threat orchestration ecosystem would be built. The algorithms will be deployed on top of a Security Information and Event Management system (SIEM) or any other security data processing tool to take advantage of the processed data.

8.4.2. Asset Description

The Response Mitigation phase utilizes neural network architectures like CNNs, RNNs, and MLPs. These networks are trained to recognize and respond to specific classes of attacks, providing an adaptive and effective security response plan. These include dynamic threat adaptation, threat prioritization, automated security mitigation, novel intrusion detection systems and advanced neural network models for response mitigation. Figure 14 provides the architecture of the AI-driven 6G Response - Mitigation functional block, including its functional block requirements-data input and output interfaces with a description.

Figure 14 - 6G AI Response Mitigation fb Architecture.

A.I. Framework for Threat Mitigation

Data:

The foundation of this framework relies on network traffic data, augmented by an additional column denoting the presence and type of threats. While various network parameters can be integrated, the critical focus lies on threat labelling within the dataset.

Mitigation Plans:

To facilitate seamless threat response, an engine is developed to map threats to their corresponding mitigation plans. This engine effectively serves as a configuration file, accommodating updates as new threats surface. The engine's design, employing if/else statements, ensures optimal performance without compromising computational efficiency.

Multi-Layer Perceptron Neural Network:

Figure 15 shows the multi-layer perceptron which includes an input layer, multiple hidden layers and an output layer for multi-label classification. The neural network can handle multiple input and outputs, thus enabling it to handle multiple threat scenarios.

Figure 15 - Multi-Layer Perceptron with multiple outputs.

The input can take both numerical and one-hot-encoded categorical variables. The pre-processing involves standardization or normalization to ensure consistent scaling. A SoftMax activation function is employed at output layer of the network for finding the probabilities for each potential threat class. Therefore, the highest probability output is selected to classify the threat type.

Post-training the model is encapsulated within a saved object, housed in an antifactory file. Upon encountering new data, pre-processing precedes the application of the trained model. The model outputs probabilities corresponding to the recommended mitigation plan(s), facilitating timely and precise threat response.

This holistic framework, encompassing data-driven threat assessment, intelligent mitigation planning, and AI-driven decision-making, stands as a testament to the transformative power of advanced algorithms in risk management and cybersecurity. By seamlessly integrating AI into threat response, this asset fortifies organizations against evolving cyber threats, exemplifying a

proactive and agile security approach. The functional architecture of the Multi-Layer Perceptron Algorithm is represented as shown below in Figure 16, with the analytical data communication steps.

Figure 16 - Functional architecture of the Multi-Layer Perceptron Algorithm.

Table 7 represents the recommended AI/ML Techniques, Datasets, and ML model’s inputs and outputs that will be utilized for developing the 6G Response-Mitigation functional block. The envisioned AI/ML models may receive inputs from Security Orchestrator (SO), Digital Twins (DT), Dynamic and automated Service Composition (DSC), and AI-driven Decision (AID) functional blocks.

Table 7 - AI/ML Models for AI 6G Response Mitigation fb.

AI/ML Technique(s)	Dataset	ML Model’s Inputs	ML Model’s Output
Multi-Layer Perceptron	Gas Pipeline (public) WUSTL-IIoT (public), 5G-NIDD (public)	SO, DT, DSC, AID	Response Mitigation Plan Attack 1
Deep Data Neural Network (DDNN)	vCDN_EDoS	SO, DT, DSC, AID	Response Mitigation Plan Attack 2
Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs)	ToN-IoT (public) 5G-NIDD (public)	SO, DT, DSC, AID	Response Mitigation Plan Attack 3
Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs),	CIC-IDS2017, CSE-CIC-IDS2018	SO, DT, DSC, AID	Response Mitigation Plan Attack 4

8.5. Slicing Mitigation Planner Service

8.5.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

In the ever-evolving landscape of network security, the role of automated systems has taken centre stage, conducting in an era of enhanced efficiency and agility [68]. This paradigm shift is particularly pronounced in the field of 5G networks, where the dynamic and extensive network topology presents a unique set of challenges [69][70]. The success of these automated systems pivots on meticulous decision planning, a vital element in every network environment, but even more crucial within the intricate web of 5G.

The use of prescriptive analytics in network security planning has emerged as a game-changing approach. Prescriptive analytics goes beyond mere data analysis to proactively suggest actions that can be taken by the security system [71]. This approach is crucial in the context of 5G networks, where timely and well-informed decisions are essential. By incorporating prescriptive analytics into the decision-making process, the security system can plan more effectively and act with greater precision, enhancing the overall resilience of the network.

Furthermore, the ability to trace the end-to-end path of a detected malicious flow is paramount in a security context, and it necessitates the correlation of the network's overall infrastructure. The correlation of network infrastructure is an essential facet of the modern security landscape, allowing security administrators to pinpoint and mitigate threats with the precision demanded by the 5G era.

UWS offers an asset within the network self-protection loop that correlates 5G network topology information with the detected malicious flow to create a mitigation plan for taking the necessary actions to counteract the incoming threat.

8.5.2. Asset Description

Within the scope of the RIGOUROUS project, UWS is developing the UWS's Slicing Mitigation Planner Service (SMPS). The design of this asset oversees the planning of mitigation policies to be executed by the system to protect the network against a known cyber threat occurring in real-time within the 5G Network.

This SMPS component is determining the appropriate actions to take and their respective locations. These actions can be diverse, including options like dropping traffic, redirecting it, mirroring the flow, or applying a slice. The location where enforcement occurs is determined based on predefined logic set by the programmer, such as 'near the source,' 'near the destination,' 'n hops from the source,' or 'E2E path.' These actions can be automated by the administrator through a policy engine to define different strategies for various types of attacks. This decision is made through the analysis of alerts triggered by the previous asset in the framework, the UWS Network Security Flow Monitoring (NSFM).

The SMPS constructs a set of decisions using an intent-based methodology, which form an integral part of the Mitigation Plan. These decisions consist of a set of instructions, extending the recorded

information on the malicious flow collected by NSFM and the network topology information related to the locations where mitigation rules should be applied. These instructions explicitly define the action to be taken, the location where the action should be implemented, the method of implementation, the duration of its activation, and the timing for its execution. For the purposes of this project, the SMPS manages the computation of the 'E2E path' locations where the attack needs to be mitigated.

Figure 17 - Sequence diagram of the architecture of the UWS Slicing Mitigation Planner Service.

The UWS's SMPS serves as the cognitive component of the Security Loop outlined in Task 4.4. It is linked to the NSFM Events interface and receives notifications for newly detected malicious flows (01 in Figure 17). After collecting the NIDS Event, the Planner component retrieves real-time Topology information from the Topology Database (02 in Figure 17). Subsequently, by combining network topology information with data from the detected malicious flow, the Planner identifies the end-to-end (E2E) path of the specific malicious flow (03 in Figure 17). Next, the Planner component generates a Decision based on the detected attack (04 in Figure 17). Through a series of Prescriptive Analytics queries, the Planner component constructs a Mitigation Plan that includes details about (05 in Figure 17):

- Where actions should be implemented along the E2E path.
- What set of actions should be taken to apply the decided network slice.
- When the set of actions should be applied in the data plane.
- For How Long the actions should be enforced in the data plane.

Lastly, the Planner component transmits the Mitigation Plan to the Plan interface (06 in Figure 17).

8.6. Mapping of AI-driven Security Response-Mitigation Assets to HLA

Figure 18 - High-Level Architecture.

Figure 18 illustrates the High-Level Architecture of the different functional blocks. As it is shown, The Response-Mitigation receives input from AI-Driven Decision regarding the type of attack that was detected by Security Analytics Engine and the decision-making that has to be taken as an action mitigation plan. Additionally, Response-Mitigation communicates with Dynamic Automated Service Composition in order to receive information about potential mismatches between the different components and share the mitigation plan. Response-Mitigation receives input from Digital Twin too, regarding the topology of the different components of the system that is simulated and shares the mitigation plan as well. Finally, it informs Slice Manager about the running results.

9 SOAR-DRIVEN NETWORK FLOW AND TOPOLOGY MONITORING

9.1. Introduction

This section outlines the work carried out during the first iteration of Task 4.4, focusing on the RIGOUROUS architectural components that play a pivotal role in achieving the task's goals and objectives. In this context, UWS elaborates on the activities related to the design and implementation of innovative network monitoring services deployed alongside the data plane. These services are instrumental in realizing the goal of establishing a Security, Orchestration, Administration, and Response (SOAR) driven network flow and topology monitoring system. The primary objective of this task is to develop and mature technologies that can effectively detect cyberattacks within a 5G network infrastructure scenario. It also involves acquiring the necessary topological information to correlate the E2E path, enabling subsequent actions to mitigate threats. The overarching objective of UWS in this task is to establish a closed and cognitive network self-protection loop for safeguarding 5G network infrastructures against incoming attacks. This goal involves the coordination of various software components within the RIGOUROUS framework. The NSFM component is responsible for detecting incoming threats and issuing alerts to other components. The Topology Inventory Agent (TIA) serves as a topology sensor, continuously reporting the real-time network topology, which is crucial for calculating the E2E path for mitigation actions. The SMPS is tasked with determining the E2E path for detected malicious flows and devising a set of decisions to mitigate the attack.

9.2. Network Security Flow Monitoring

9.2.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

Signature-based Network Intrusion Detection System have long been in the research field of network security, offering a robust line of defence by the capabilities of identifying known threats and attack patterns and vulnerabilities.

In parallel, anomaly-based NIDS have emerged as a valuable addition to the security area, able to detect novel threats that could evade signature-based systems. Nevertheless, the efficacy of anomaly detectors remains limited in addressing the full spectrum of security challenges. Additionally, the signature-based NIDS still have room to be improved, as they are commonly used in most organizations and companies as a first line of defence.

As we stand at the threshold of the 5G era, the network infrastructure is set to undergo transformative changes. The introduction of 5G networks brings with it a host of new vulnerabilities and attack vectors. Surprisingly, most existing NIDS (signature-based or anomaly detection-based) do not provide flow information regarding to the unique requirements of 5G networks.

According to Cloudflare, the network security company holding more than 96% of the market share [72], DDoS attacks now constitute the majority of network layer attack traffic on the

internet. Surprisingly, approximately 55% of these threats originate from mobile devices rather than desktop devices [73]. This underscores the need for the development and enhancement of security systems to effectively operate and detect threats in 5G mobile environments.

To achieve this goal, UWS is working on enhancing the capabilities of the Next-Generation NIDS to detect known DDoS attacks in 5G scenarios while providing detailed information about the malicious network flow.

9.2.2. Asset Description

Within the scope of the RIGOUROUS project, UWS is developing the UWS Network Security Flow Monitoring asset. This software component is designed to detect potential cyberattacks and threats within a 5G network infrastructure.

The NSFPM enhances the traditional capabilities of NIDS, such as Snort, to achieve fine-grained detection of known DDoS attacks within the 5G Network infrastructure. It accomplishes this by matching sensed network flows against various signatures stored in the NIDS database. This enhancement is achieved through two subcomponents: (I) a traditional NIDS with an updated rules database for known DDoS attacks and (II) the NextGen NIDS, which serves as a wrapper for NIDS alerts and provides the system with data on the detected malicious flows. This asset supports not only traditional IP networks but also overlay networks commonly used in cloud infrastructures, such as Generic Routing Encapsulation (GRE), Virtual Extensible Local Area Network (VXLAN), Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation (GENEVE), Virtual Local Area Network (VLAN), as well as those used in cellular and IoT mobile operator networks, such as the GPRS Tunnelling Protocol (GTP).

Figure 19 - Sequence diagram of the architecture of the UWS Network Security Flow Monitoring.

The UWS’s NSFM component functions as a flow sensor with capabilities that surpass traditional NIDS. It identifies signature-based threats within the network and collects detailed metadata on the detected malicious flow. The component's workflow is illustrated in Figure 19.

The NIDS reads a new network flow (01 in Figure 19) and searches in the NIDS Rules database a signature that matches the flow (02 in Figure 19). When the NIDS identifies a matching rule, it logs the newly detected intrusion using the Unified2 protocol (03 in Figure 19).

The NextGen NIDS subcomponent is designed to continuously monitor and read each new record in the Unified2 log file (04 in Figure 19). The Unified2 Watcher, once a new intrusion is recorded, pushes a notification to the NextGen NIDS subcomponent with the NIDS alert information (05 in Figure 19). Then, the NextGen NIDS dissects the malicious flow in search of every overlay network information (06 in Figure 19). Using the collected network flow information and the NIDS alert, the NextGen NIDS constructs an NSFM Event (07 in Figure 19) and forwards it to the NSFM Events interface (08 in Figure 19).

9.3. Topology Inventory Agent

9.3.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

In the ever-evolving landscape of network security, the foremost principle remains unchanged - a proactive approach is essential for safeguarding against an increasingly complex array of threats. At the heart of this approach lies the necessity for a clear understanding of network topology and the countless devices that occupy it.

Networks today surpass traditional boundaries, and within the context of 5G, this interconnectivity is amplified to an extraordinary scale. Diverse stakeholders, applications, and technologies coexist within the same network topology, creating a dynamic and complex ecosystem.

A fundamental aspect of securing a complex network topology is the ability to sense and provide precise information about every component that populates it. This includes hosts, devices, routers, bridges, and a collection of network elements. The sheer granularity of network topology information empowers security administrators and systems to make informed decisions and to tailor their security measures with pinpoint accuracy. As we delve deeper into the core of modern network security, it becomes evident that the role of network topology in threat mitigation cannot be overstated. The granularity of information about the network's composition allows security measures to be fine-tuned and rendered more specific, thus providing a robust defence against evolving threats.

Rojas et al. [74] introduced the Tree Exploration Discovery Protocol (TEDP) as a viable alternative to the Link-Layer Discovery Protocol (LLDP). Through their work, they demonstrated TEDP's capability to construct shortest paths simultaneously while gathering topology information, without additional messaging compared to LLDP. The paper not only analysed two distinct TEDP implementations but also offered valuable insights into essential features that SDN platforms should ideally provide for an efficient topology discovery service, addressing the nuances of overlay networks.

NMSaaS⁷ presents a comprehensive network discovery software utilizing diverse protocols, including Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP), Cisco Discovery Protocol (CDP), Windows Management Instrumentation (WMI), Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP), and VMware, to uncover IT assets. The software dynamically creates maps based on Layer 2 and Layer 3 connections, and its integration with hypervisors allows for the discovery of virtual assets. This reference provides an essential overview of a powerful network discovery tool with a wide array of capabilities.

SolarWinds' Network Topology Mapper⁸ software emerges as a robust solution for automatic network topology delineation. Supporting various discovery methods, including SNMP, ICMP, WMI, CDP, VMware, and more, it offers comprehensive reports on switch ports, VLANs, subnets, and inventory. Notably, it directly addresses compliance requirements such as PCI and FIPS 140-2, providing a valuable tool for maintaining up-to-date network diagrams.

Toufga et al. [75] present a significant contribution by introducing an effective topology discovery service tailored for Software-Defined Vehicular Networks. Criticizing the limitations of the prevalent OpenFlow-based topology discovery service in vehicular networks, they propose crucial

⁷ <https://www.nmsaas.com>

⁸ <https://www.solarwinds.com/network-topology-mapper>

directions for overcoming these challenges. This reference underscores the importance of adapting topology discovery services to the specific demands of vehicular networks, providing a foundation for further research in this domain.

Existing solutions lack the prowess to seamlessly facilitate the creation of this dynamic 5G network. None adequately addresses the discovery and tracking of 5G users navigating antennas, the rapid VM migrations altering topology, and the crucial discovery of specialized hardware like radio equipment. This multifaceted challenge demands a novel approach, transcending current solutions' limitations.

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To address the absence of topology sensing, UWS is introducing an asset that delves into the discovery of 5G and beyond network topologies. This addition aims to enhance the decision-making process for the self-protection cognitive loop within the RIGOUROUS project.

9.3.2. Asset Description

Within the scope of the RIGOUROUS project, UWS is developing the UWS Topology Inventory Agent (TIA) asset, which functions as a sensor for collecting topological information related to the 5G Network infrastructure. It is designed to be distributed alongside the network and should be deployed on the same machines as the data plane, where instances of NSFM and UWS Slicing Control Agent (SCA) are also located. TIA is responsible for discovering the network's topology. With this information, SMPS can identify E2E path of the malicious flow detected by NSFM and transmit the Mitigation Plan to the relevant components and assets.

Figure 20 - Sequence diagram of the architecture of the UWS Topology Inventory Agent.

The UWS Topology Inventory Agent (TIA) component supervises the provision of fine-grained topology information regarding the network infrastructure's actors, including routers, switches, hosts, and more.

At specified intervals, the Topology Collector subcomponent reads the topology (01 in Figure 20) and checks with the Topology Database for any changes that need to be reported (02 and 03 in Figure 20). If there are any changes to report, the Topology Collector will update the Topology Database with this new information (04 in Figure 20). Once the new topology information is added to the database, the Topology Collector sends a notification to the Topology Sender (05 in Figure 20), which then forwards the topology information to the Topology interface (06 in Figure 20).

9.4. Mapping of SOAR-driven Network Flow and Topology Monitoring Assets to HLA

The diagram provided in this section illustrates the interaction and communication among various components within the RIGOUROUS architecture, including functional modules and services. Its primary function is to establish an E2E network slice within the data plane. Notably, this diagram corresponds to the reactive workflow delineated in deliverable D2.1. Consequently, the enforcement of an E2E slice within the data plane occurs reactively, triggered specifically when a cyber-attack is detected within the network infrastructure.

The information gathered by the UWS Topology Inventory Agent (TIA), within the Data Monitoring (DM) Service, is stored by Data Services (DS). Consequently, the TIA pushes the new topological information (1 in Figure 21) to the UWS Slicing Mitigation Planner Service (SMPS) within the AI-Driven Decision (AID) Service.

Upon detection of a threat in the data plane by the UWS Network Security Flow Monitoring (NSFM), an alert in the form of an NSFM event is generated and transmitted to the AID (2 in Figure 21). This event includes comprehensive information concerning the identified malicious network flow, spanning the B5G infrastructure and overlay networks, along with metadata detailing the nature of the alert.

The SMPS will engage in prescriptive analysis to compute the E2E path across the network infrastructure associated with the identified malicious flow. Subsequently, it will construct a new Mitigation Plan and transmit it to the AI-Driven Security Orchestrator (SO) using the MSPL policy language (3 in Figure 21). The SO, in turn, delivers the newly formulated and verified Mitigation Plan to be enforced by the Response Mitigation (RM) Service (4 in Figure 21). This RM serves as a collection of reactive actuators equipped with response mechanisms tailored for mitigating attacks.

The RM service executes the specified Mitigation Policies by selecting the corresponding Security Agent. In this process, the Slice Manager component receives the Mitigation Policies (5 in Figure 21) containing adequate information required to implement the network slice along the E2E path. Additionally, the Slice Manager offers an abstract view of the data plane, concealing the underlying technologies coexisting within the data plane. The Slice Manager then enforces the network slice (6 in Figure 21). To accomplish this, the Slice Manager translates the received intent message into a series of actions specific to the technology employed by the security data plane agent where the network slice is set to be enforced (7 in Figure 21).

Upon successful creation of the network slice, the Security Agents transmit an acknowledgment (ACK) message to the preceding architectural components to communicate the successful implementation of the enforced rules (8 and 9 in Figure 21).

Figure 21 - Sequence Diagram for creating an E2E network slice for single and multi-domain 6G infrastructures automatically.

10 ROBUST AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING AI

10.1. Introduction

The use of AI/ML techniques is in the core of RIGOUROUS's assets to empower intelligent and fully automated security management services. As detailed in the previous sections, AI plays a key role in enabling anomaly detection, decision, and mitigation capabilities in RIGOUROUS framework. Moreover, RIGOUROUS is promoting CTI sharing as a crucial service that help in collecting and analysing pertinent data about potential threats, vulnerabilities, and attacker tactics. However, AI-powered systems and CTI sharing raise security and privacy issues. To address these concerns, RIGOUROUS is developing a set of advanced assets that strengthen AI robustness and improve privacy preservation. Particularly, three assets will be developed to (i) enable proactive protection of ML models against poisoning attacks using the emerging MTD paradigm; (ii) provide a cloud-native based EaaS cryptographic services, including homomorphic encryption, to IoT devices/gateways; and (iii) empower privacy-preserving CTI sharing leveraging anonymization PETs, such as K-anonymity, T-closeness, and suppression.

The remaining of this section elaborates on RIGOUROUS's Robust AI and privacy-preserving assets and their mapping to functional blocks of RIGOUROUS's high level architecture. For each asset, we highlight how the asset advances the existing state-of-the-art, and provide detailed description of the asset.

10.2. MTD-based Robust ML Model(s)

10.2.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

Some studies in the literature of computer science provide security mechanisms for FL. Differential privacy methods add noise to the data to obscure sensitive information. However, the noise can be itself a source of vulnerability for attacks [76]. In Byzantine attack, adversaries can trigger poisoning or backdoor attacks through forwarding malicious messages to the server, to endanger the security of the model. In this direction, robust rules (e.g., [77], [78]) are utilized in FL, that mainly apply outlier detection methods to remove malicious models. However, these defense methods are still vulnerable against new emerging attacks. To reduce the computation cost of outlier detection methods, a shuffling-based defense method that isolates the attackers from ordinary users, has been studied in [79]. Some studies have addressed both privacy of participants and robustness issues, e.g., [80], [81], [82].

FL has also been studied in the context of edge computing, e.g., 6G digital twin [83], vehicular networks [84], and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) networks [85]. However, these studies assume a secure network environment without any malicious behaviour. Blockchain technology can provide secure storage solutions [86]. The integration of blockchain and FL in the context of edge/cloud computing has been studied in [87], [88], [89], [90], and [91]. These approaches enhance the security of FL through providing verification and consensus-based techniques to verify elements involved in FL e.g., participant devices, models, aggregator-servers. Either the

computer science approaches or designed FL approaches for edge computing, advocate a reactive scenario that operate based on malicious behaviour detection and mitigation. RIGOUROUS goes a step forward by applying a proactive scenario, and making FL as a moving target which makes the triggering of the malicious behaviour difficult.

10.2.2. Asset Description

This asset provides a security-enhanced FL approach to perform collaborative learning objectives e.g., anomaly detection behaviour, in edge computing environment in a secure manner. To this end, a Moving Target Defense (MTD) strategy will be used to enhance the security of learning process against adversarial attacks e.g., poisoning attack. Input data will be some dataset batches distributed among devices, with a list of features related to the learning objective e.g., traffic features that contribute to DDoS attack detection. These input features are used to train the learning model. Network topology, as well as machine learning parameters will also be given as input. The output will be the inference result e.g., accuracy of anomaly detection., as well as the performance of the model in prohibiting the potential attacks.

A representation of the learning process has been illustrated in Figure 22. The system includes an edge aggregator offered by MEC servers, which offers aggregation service to devices of mobile network, under its radio communication coverage. The models are trained locally at devices, then the model parameters are transmitted to the edge aggregator for the aggregation, using an algorithm such as FedAvg. There will be multiple iterations between edge aggregator and the devices until the learning process be converged.

MTD strategy for federated learning will be developed as an MTD layer on top of FL application layer. The MTD strategy dynamically manages the potential surfaces for attacks, with the objective of minimizing the probability of potential attacks e.g., model poisoning attack that might be triggered from a subset of malicious participants. Accordingly, appropriate MTD controlling signals will be triggered to dynamically apply the FL configurations for model training and parameter aggregation. A multi-model policy exploitation in FL, and the required coordination among models to realize the objective of the FL (e.g., DDoS attack detection), will form the MTD strategy. Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) will be exploited to design the MTD strategy and generate the MTD controlling signals, while considering the criteria including accuracy of the learning objective (e.g., DDoS attack detection), and the probability of potential attacks. Dataset, attack, and features for MTD-based robust federated learning are summarized in Table 8. The asset will investigate the extension of the model to include also central cloud in the hierarchy of FL.

Figure 22 - Functional architecture of MTD-based Robust Federated Learning.

Table 8 – Dataset, attack, and features for MTD-based robust federated learning.

Adversarial Threat	AI/ML Technique(s)	Dataset(s)	ML Model's Inputs	ML Model's Output
Poisoning Attack	FL	CICDDoS 2019 [92]	A subset of 87 traffic IP features including source/destination IP addresses/ports, protocols, flow packet statistics, flag-related information etc.	DDoS attack detection

10.3. Encryption-as-a-Service

10.3.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

In recent evaluations, it has been demonstrated that various Encryption-as-a-Service (EaaS) solutions face challenges, such as limitations in centralized processes and scalability. As the demand for robust data security in diverse domains grows, there is a need for more adaptable EaaS frameworks.

The diverse EaaS solutions reviewed contribute to data security in specific domains. One solution

explores quantum cryptography [93], facing limitations in centralized processes and scalability. Another utilizes a multi-cloud security model but has flexibility and complexity issues [94]. Another EaaS contribution in smart substations has layered legacy device encryption but is limited in scalability, cloud-native adaptability, and user-friendliness [95]. Healthcare cloud security integrates private cloud cryptographic services but lacks some cloud-native features and flexibility [96]. The framework for mobile cloud security focuses on encryption but has limitations in architecture, scalability, and user-friendliness [97]. Cloud-native encryption for Kubernetes Pods raises concerns about resource utilization and responsiveness [98]. A solution with shared cryptographic accelerators optimizes resources and response times but faces scalability and flexibility challenges [99]. The microservices architecture based smart grid framework lacks cloud-native features, user-friendliness, and flexibility [100].

In the context of RIGOROUS, our proposed EaaS solution fills the gaps identified in existing works by offering a cloud-native, fully customizable, easy-to-deploy, and manageable solution for resource-constrained devices. By leveraging the latest advancements in cloud technologies and providing extensive customization options from encryption algorithms to deployment architecture choices, our solution aims to provide a robust and efficient encryption service.

10.3.2. Asset Description

The EaaS asset represents a cloud-native solution designed specifically to deliver secure and efficient encryption services for protecting data of IoT devices/gateways. Its purpose is to provide a comprehensive solution that addresses the diverse encryption requirements of IoT service providers, ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of data transmitted by IoT devices.

The goal of the EaaS asset consists in enabling each subscribed IoT service provider (IoT SP) to establish its own customized EaaS instance(s). This instance will be customized according to their specific subscription parameters, such as encryption/decryption algorithms (e.g., symmetric, asymmetric, homomorphic), number of instances needed, deployment method (i.e., cloud-based, edge-based), and geographical area of service (i.e., preferred locations of edge servers), granting IoT SPs both flexibility and control. The EaaS asset also grants the infrastructure's administrators the ability to troubleshoot and monitor the health of the asset through a user-friendly web platform.

Figure 23 - Functional architecture of EaaS Platform.

As illustrated in Figure 23, the *EaaS Orchestrator* acts as a link between the *EaaS Web Platform* and the *EaaS Virtualized Infrastructure*. Its main function is to automatically translate the parameters provided by the IoT SP to the Controller of the EaaS Virtualized Infrastructure, ensuring the proper bootstrapping of the corresponding instance(s).

Once subscribed to the EaaS platform, the IoT SPs are provided with the API entry point for their instance's Request Handler. This entry point serves as the endpoint through which the IoT SPs can interact with their instances.

When the instance is created and ready, the IoT SP can send encryption/decryption requests in JSON format to the Request Handler whenever they need to encrypt or decrypt the IoT data.

Request format:

```
{
  "id": "iot id",
  "algo": "encryption algorithm",
  ##### encrypt request
  "text": "text to encrypt",
  ### decrypt request
  "cipher": "cipher to decrypt"
}
```

The IoT object will receive accordingly:

Response format:

```
{“id”: “iot id” ,  
  “algo” : “encryption algorithm”,  
  ##### encrypt request  
  “cipher” : “encrypted text” ,  
  ### decrypt request  
  “text” : “decrypted cipher”  
}
```

10.4. Privacy-preserving CTI Sharing

10.4.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

Cyber Threat Information (CTI) contains, in most cases, sensitive information that should not be exchanged with third parties, or at least should be protected before the transmission. For instance, Personally Identifiable Information (PII) that could be used to compromise a stakeholder participating in the sharing scenario [101]. To solve this problem, a mechanism to protect the sensitive attributes to be exchanged has to be used. In this line, authors in [102] propose an ecosystem to store threat files in a secure and trusted way using a combination of HyperLedger Fabric and InterPlanetary File System (IPFS). But, the receivers of the information, although trusted, can still access the sensitive information. Others [103] present a scheme where signatures are used to hide participants' identities, but the information itself remains unprotected. Lastly, authors in [104] present a custom protocol for CTI sharing, using homomorphic encryption to protect sensitive information, to be used in the training of a classifier, but they do not make use of any standard Threat Intelligence Platform (TIP) in their architecture.

In our case, a privacy-preserving Cyber Threat Information sharing solution, based on the combination of a policy-based anonymization module which can apply several widely-used PETs, and a standard TIP such as Threat Intelligence Sharing Platform (MISP), is proposed to enable a secure exchanging of CTI information in the context of RIGOUROUS. This asset, initially developed in the context of CyberSec4Europe, will be evolved from a TRL 3 to a TRL 5, and adapted to the needs of this project.

10.4.2. Asset Description

The asset is composed by the following three modules:

1. **Anonymizer Service:** it will receive, from the Data Services module, the CTI information to be shared, and from the Policy Management Service, the privacy policies to be applied. It will create a MISP event from the received CTI information and, based on the policy, it will

- apply the corresponding PET to the specified attributes, generating a protected MISP event.
2. **Policy Management Service:** it will collect the privacy requirements to be applied received from the AI-driven Security Orchestrator and generate the corresponding policies to be sent to the Anonymizer Service.
 3. **TIP Proxy:** acts as a proxy between the local MISP server and the other modules, i.e., Anonymizer Service or Data Services. It will be in charge of communicating with MISP to send and receive events.

In addition, the TIP platform (MISP) is also inside the asset scope and will be synchronized with other platforms (from foreign domains) to enable the CTI federation so that locally generated events can reach their final destinations and foreign events can reach the local domain.

The workflow to send new CTI information starts at the modules that generate the information, i.e., the AI-driven Security Analytics Engine (SAE), or the AI-driven Decision Engine (AID). Data Services module receives the information and decides to send it unprotected, for which it will directly communicate with the TIP Proxy since no anonymization is needed at all, or with the Anonymizer Service in case any sensitive attribute protection is required. In this case, the Anonymizer Service will apply the techniques specified in the privacy policies that it has previously received from the Policy Management Service (previously generated based on the privacy requirements sent by the orchestrator), generating a protected MISP event that will be published in the local MISP platform by communicating with the TIP Proxy.

On the other hand, events received from foreign organizations will reach the local MISP platform and will be received by the TIP Proxy, which will send the information to the Data Services. This information can be crucial to improve, for instance, the behaviour of the models deployed within the SAE.

These two workflows can be consulted in Figure 24, where the asset architecture is shown.

The list of PETs supported by the Anonymizer Service contain: K-anonymity, L-diversity, T-closeness, suppression, and generalization. Which one to use will depend on the information to be shared and the privacy requirements.

Figure 24 - Function architecture of Privacy-preserving Cyber Threat Information Sharing (UMU).

10.5. Mapping of Robust and Privacy-Preserving AI Assets to HLA

Figure 25 - Mapping of Robust and Privacy-Preserving AI assets to RIGOUROUS's HLA.

As depicted in Figure 25, the robust AI and privacy preserving assets implement the functionalities of the “MTD-based Robust AI” and “Privacy-preserving CTI Sharing” functional blocks. It is worth mentioning that the EaaS platform is a new functional block in RIGOUROUS’s framework, allowing

to deliver encryption services for data collected from IoT devices/gateways as well as homomorphic-encryption based privacy enhancing that can be outsourced to build privacy-preserving AI/ML models able to process encrypted data. For instance, the homomorphic encryption service can be used to encrypt the model parameters exchanged during the FL training of the anomaly detection service in AI-Driven Security Analytics Engine (SAE), or for encrypting data fed into ML models integrated incorporated in AI-driven Decision (AID) and AI-Driven Security Orchestrator (SO).

11 CYBER SECURITY TESTING AND TWINNING

11.1. Introduction

The effect that Digital Twins have on industrial infrastructure is impressive. Combined with IoT technologies, big data analytics and artificial intelligence, have led to significant benefits in terms of productivity. The Digital Twins enable the capture of a virtual representation of the components and operation of an IoT device throughout its life cycle. By applying the Digital Twins in an industrial environment, the integration between IoT and data analysis can be resolved and visualized.

RHEA Group's **Cyber Integration, Test and Evaluation Framework (CITEF™)** is a cyber-range environment creating and running an exact representation of IT and networking technology assets, hence leveraging cybersecurity testing activity at any stage of the development, security, and operations (DevSecOps) lifecycle.

11.2. CITEF - Cyber Integration, Test and Evaluation Framework

11.2.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

In establishing a state-of-the-art Zero-touch network [105], RIGOUROUS project is leveraging service automation to unleash the business potential of 5G and beyond while guaranteeing the security of both managed customer network(s) and managing environment. System modelling and data-driven test and simulation means are a necessity to support the DevSecOps life cycle of RIGOUROUS assets to meet the project's objective of a fully autonomous operation driven environment enabling self-configuration, self-monitoring and threat detection, self-healing and self-optimization including autonomous AI driven risk remediation, without direct human intervention. The validation of such dynamic design and its adaptation to ever changing threats and operational conditions requires the project to setup a digital twin where attack scenarios can be tested or safely replayed. This allows rapidly validating new security rules or threat mitigation, so the overall RIGOUROUS security posture remains optimal against a dynamic threat context.

11.2.2. Asset Description

CITEF provides a comprehensive sandbox environment to build a realistic, fully functional, safe, and legal emulation of complex and critical networking infrastructures such as RIGOUROUS. It is also possible to interconnect the simulated/emulated components to real local networks, systems, tools, and applications.

Once the representation of the networking infrastructure is built, an interactive platform permits to define complex attack scenarios and to run them step by step to validate the security architecture of the system under consideration or to provide quantified information about vulnerabilities given specific or new threats.

The CITEF mode of operation can be described as such:

1. **Building and configuring the networking infrastructure to be tested and validated.** CITEF includes a library of standard Information and Operation Technology (IT/OT) along with networking components IT/OT. It provides also design tools so each tenant of the simulated environment can build and tailor a perfect replica of its system or component. Also interfaces to real components can be set to build a comprehensive infrastructure in a cyber-physical rig (virtual plus physical assets) ready to be tested.
2. **Building the cyberattack scenarios as an overlay** onto the representation of the tested infrastructure built in step 1. The test team can build a wide range of scenarios, including:
 - a. Anomaly and errors injection into the control systems to simulate a compromised asset or resource.
 - b. Building complex tactics, techniques, and procedures (TTP) which can be automatically “fired” to validate the infrastructure security posture and response.
 - c. Testing and demonstrating the effectiveness of the security measures to facilitate the DevSecOps lifecycle and ease the implementation of Zero Trust security policies or standards.
3. **Monitoring and adapting the attack scenario.** The monitoring web interface permits the test team to analyse step by step the scenario progress, including ongoing evaluation, and to adapt the system security posture or the adversary TTP as required. This comprehensive approach ensures not only the testing and adaptation of the security system but also the evaluation of its effectiveness in response to the adversary’s actions, allowing us to validate the entire testing and assessment loop.

A visual representation of CITEF’s GUI is depicted in Figure 26, which provides an overview of the CITEF’s mode of operation in a holistic context, highlighting the CITEF’s capability to build simulation environments and create different cyberattack scenarios, while allowing users to actively monitor their scenarios in real time.

Figure 26 - CITEF GUI example representation.

11.3. Digital Twin

11.3.1. State of the Art Analysis and RIGOUROUS Advancements

IoT technology has shown impressive growth in recent years. Increasing interest has led to development of Digital Twins that are able to simulate IoT environments. In [106], researchers propose the SimIoT which extends simulation toolkit interactions occurring within the IoT-enabled healthcare context. SimIoT is based on the SimIC simulation toolkit but also includes the IoT layer that incorporates IoT devices that generate data for the private clouds. In [107], researchers present IOTSim which enables simulation of IoT big data processing using MapReduce model. In that way they provide a simulator that can support IoT applications in cloud environment. Another

tool that can be used to simulate IoT networks is OMNeT++⁹, which is a simulation library that can provide network simulation models that are available in several external frameworks.

These tools are static which means that do not use real-time data, that could cause changes to the simulation without the need to start a new one.

11.3.2. Asset Description

In the context of RIGOUROUS, we will develop a digital twin that can simulate real-time transmission of data from heterogeneous sources. The DT will provide that topology as input to the Dynamic Automated Service Composition, which will detect possible mismatches between the different components and their causes. This simulation has annotations for interoperability and security, privacy, and trust requirements. Additionally, there will be interfaces based on Rest API in order to be able to communicate with Dynamic Automated Service Composition.

11.4. Mapping of Cyber Security Testing and Twinning Assets to HLA

Figure 27 - Digital Twin interfaces.

Figure 27 shows the interfaces of the Digital Twin. It provides the topology of the network as input to Dynamic Automation Service Composition so that it can detect possible mismatches between the different components and inform Response Mitigation. The Response mitigation proposes corrective actions, and the Digital Twin sends the new topology to the Dynamic Automated Service Composition.

CITEF, as a comprehensive cyber-range environment can provide support throughout the complete DevSecOps life cycle. During the design and development phase CITEF can be used to build complex attack scenarios, allowing to validate the security architecture of the application or system under development. During the operational phase, CITEF can be used to replay real attacks under a controlled and safe environment to confirm the effectiveness of the implemented security features or to define the necessary mitigation steps.

⁹ <https://omnetpp.org/>

12 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable presented the initial outcomes of activities conducted in WP4's tasks, including the first analysis and design of RIGOUROUS's assets developed within WP4's tasks to enable AI-driven anomaly detection, decision, and mitigation in RIGOUROUS framework. The assets have been grouped into six categories according to their functionalities and the services they are delivering. Specifically, WP4's assets belong to one of the following categories: (1) *AI-driven collaborative anomaly detection while fostering privacy preservation*; (2) *AI-driven cognitive security decision-making, orchestration and management*; (3) *AI-driven security response and mitigation*; (4) *SOAR-driven network flow and topology monitoring*; (5) *AI robustness and privacy preservation*; and (6) *cybersecurity testing and digital twinning*.

For each asset, the innovations the asset introduces compared to the current state-of-the-art are emphasized. Then, a detailed description of the asset is provided, including its functional workflow and the key enabled technologies/paradigms adopted to implement the asset. The deliverable discussed also how WP4's assets map to the functional blocks of RIGOUROUS's high level architecture described in deliverable D2.1.

This deliverable serves as a foundation for the implementation of WP4's assets. Details on the initial implementation aspects and achieved scientific outcomes of WP4's assets will be reported in the upcoming D4.2 (First results of the AI-driven anomaly detection, decision, and mitigation) planned by M18.

WP4's assets will be demonstrated through RIGOUROUS's use cases (UC) which are defined in D2.2 and will be show cased in WP5. In which UC a WP4's asset will be integrated is an ongoing activity that the outcome will be reported initially in D2.2 and later on in WP5's deliverables.

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